

Appendix A Business Vocabulary Checker Test Forms

Appendix A-1 Pre-test information gathering form

The screenshot shows a web browser window displaying a Google Form titled "Business Vocabulary Checker Test". The browser's address bar shows the URL: https://docs.google.com/spreadsheets/viewform?id=en_US&formkey=dGNuWnR2YzRrczI0QSNHakUMUUDzGmQ#gid=0. The form content includes:

Business Vocabulary Checker Test

The following Questionnaire/Test has been written to gauge the performance of a proposed business vocabulary conformity checker.

You will be presented by three passages of text that are proceeded by a set of 4 questions each. After this you will be presented by a further three passages of text, these ones have been corrected by some computer software to conform to a business vocabulary standard. Each of these are also proceeded by a set of 4 questions each.

PLEASE DO NOT:

- Use the browser or form objects back button
- Close the test and restart it
- Look up the answers on the internet

(The test is monitored to ensure this)

Thank you for participating in this research, it is much appreciated

*** Required**

What sex are you?*

Male

Female

How old are you?*

Younger than 20

20-29

30-39

40-49

50-59

Older than 59

Have you ever studied in (multiple options allowed):

Sales / marketing

Engineering

Information Technology

Have you ever worked in (multiple options allowed):

Sales / marketing

Engineering

Information Technology

Business Vocabulary Checker Test

Test Passage 1a

Read the following passage of text and then click next

The following report has been produced for the benefit of the in-house stakeholders of the AWP-66 programme. It is the responsibility of Department managers to circulate this as required.

The company saw an uptake of interest in tangible products steadily during the first quarter; this is mainly regarded as a result of the increased PSS training expenditure and the appointment of Gary Fox as head of discipline. These events have helped increase interest in the AWP-66 programme. This is good news, especially because of the looming funding crisis its up against. It has already been suggested that reduced need for canvassing and A&P expenditure could save up the programme up to 20%. However, it has not reduced the expenditure needed to improve B2B sales. As per predictions during the last quarter of 2010 lead-time is up 8% due to disruptions during the holiday season. This is expected to fall back to mid 2010 levels for Q2; which will bring it back on track with the yearly target. It's a positive start to the sales year and should continue to increase as the expected order intake is met. Let me take this opportunity to thank all of those that have put so much in to make it a successful first quarter.

Business Vocabulary Checker Test

* Required

Questions 1a

In the context of the passage of text tangible products are *

- Physical products (not services)
- Products and services available today
- Products that are financially successful
- Products sold as services

In the context of the passage what does PSS stand for *

- Personal sales standard
- Professional sales skills
- Profitable selling strategy
- Practical selling support

In the context of the passage what does A&P stand for *

- Artistry and Printing
- Advertising and Promotion
- Awareness and Publications
- Practical selling support

In the context of the passage what is meant by canvassing *

- The sale of a product to a customer who has contacted the company
- The first time you make a deal with a customer
- The first time you call a potential customer
- When a potential customer is lost

Business Vocabulary Checker Test

Test Passage 2a

Read the following passage of text and then click next

The UAV will fly 6 sorties over the course of the week, with an average of 4 serials per sortie. The trials management team will be heading to the base on the 24th of March and the Algo team will be joining them on April 4th after the trials team have had some time to get the equipment sorted out. The Algo team will need to liaise with the trials management team at around 0800 to begin regression testing the SW. They will bring the required platform parameters executable. The engagements we are most interested in are ones where the UAV is evading engagement; if any of these are not captured there could be some serious development repercussions.

The trials management team will require the PIIPs documentation before the 23rd of March so they can take it on to the base. This will need to be collected as it's too sensitive to put through the post. The exec will be on site on April 5th taking the customer through the new improvements, so could everyone onsite be welcoming and professional. This is all depending on the prevailing winds from the SW, which if too strong could see engagements postponed till the following week.

Business Vocabulary Checker Test

* Required

Questions 2a

A UAV would most typically be used for *

- Private Jet
- Surveillance Operations
- Rescue Helicopter
- Passenger Jet

What is a primary responsibility of the 'Algo' team *

- Testing their mathematical formulas work with the software
- Checking that the Software renders properly
- Testing the software runs in different environments
- Testing that the software does what its meant too

In the context of the text, what is a sortie? *

- A slang term for getting everything sorted out
- A sequence of random flight events
- The time a vehicle is in the air
- The time a vehicle needs to be serviced

In the context of the text, what is a serial? *

- A series of planned activities
- A Code that is needed before a sortie can take place
- A name given to the unique identifier of a UAV
- An arbitrary unit of time assigned to a sortie

The third paragraph of text documents the resetting of a server and carrying out a software upgrade. It has originated from the IT department.

Business Vocabulary Checker Test

Test Passage 3a

Read the following passage of text then click next

Over the next few weeks disruption of the intranet, internet and email system may be experienced. There should be no disruption to the VoIP system.

The root cause of this is the reset of the Active Directory server due to an influx of new users over the past month. The machines next to the IT area on floor 2 provide a bridge to the Oxford office LAN should you need to connect to the internet urgently. In addition to the Active Directory server being reset the network switches are being upgraded to accept a high throughput rate. This should reduce the bottleneck effect that the current system is presenting users. Efforts are being made to reduce the disruption to the email service which is additionally affected by the upgrading of the MTA software which will stop the outgoing SMTP server from working from 10pm on the 17th of February for roughly 6 hours. The Intranet should remain least affected as it does not require the Active Directory server for user authentication. You may however experience problems connecting to external resources that are linked to from the intranet. It may also be an issue to connect to the intranet via VPN from your home laptop.

As always every effort will be made to reduce the disturbances. We appreciate your corporation during this time of change.

Appendix A-7 Information Technology – Uncorrected Passage Questions

The screenshot shows a web browser window with several tabs open: Gmail, Google Docs - Home, Business Vocabulary Checker, Business Vocabulary Checker, and Dissertation - Prototype [m]. The address bar shows a Google Docs spreadsheet URL. The main content area displays a form titled "Business Vocabulary Checker Test".

Business Vocabulary Checker Test

* Required

Questions 3a

In the context of the passage what is VoIP *

- The companies internet phone system
- The name of the companies intranet
- A technology that delivers the intranet
- A voice activated desktop assistant

In the context of the passage what is Active Directory *

- The companies computer based address book
- The software that makes used appear in their email application
- Something that manages user accounts and access rights
- A file managing application

In the context of the passage what is a Bridge *

- The join between two networks
- The physical merging of two offices
- Software that makes it possible to connect to another company owned computer
- The hardware that allows you to access the intranet

In the context of the passage what is a LAN *

- Load Accessible Network
- Logical Algorithm Neuron
- Local Area Network
- Land Available Network

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Business Vocabulary Checker Test

Test Passage 1b

Read the following passage of text then click next

The following report has been produced for the benefit of the in-house stakeholders of the AWP-66 programme. It is the responsibility of Department managers to circulate this as required.

The company saw an uptake of interest in currently available products and services steadily during the first quarter; this is mainly regarded as a result of the increased Professional Selling Skills (PSS) training expenditure and the appointment of Gary Fox as head of discipline. These events have helped increase interest in the AWP-66 programme. This is good news, especially because of the looming funding crisis its up against. It has already been suggested that reduced need for cold calling and advertising and promotion (A&P) expenditure could save up the programme up to 20%. However, it has not reduced the expenditure needed to improve Business to Business (B2B) sales. As per predictions during the last quarter of 2010 lead time (time between order and provision of goods or service) is up 8% due to disruptions during the holiday season. This is expected to fall back to mid 2010 levels for 2nd Quarter; which will bring it back on track with the yearly sales target. It's a positive start to the sales year and should continue to increase as the expected order intake is met. Let me take this opportunity to thank all of those that have put so much in to make it a successful 1st quarter.

Business Vocabulary Checker Test

* Required

Questions 1b

In the context of the passage what does lead time refer to *

- The time it takes to contact a potential customer
- The time between ordering a product and its delivery
- The time between a product being offered and it being bought
- The average time it takes for the leading sales team member to sell a product

In the context of the passage What does Q2 stand for *

- The second quarter of a year
- A product that is offered for sale
- The second tier of managers in a management hierarchy
- The code name of the sales division

In the context of the passage what does B2B stand for *

- Buyer to Buyer
- Bid to Bill
- Business to Business
- Bench to Breech

In the context of the passage what is meant by target *

- The target audience of a product
- The amount of sales that must be met
- Its used in both way above
- Its not used in either way above

Business Vocabulary Checker Test

Text Passage 2b

Read the following passage of text and then click next

The Unmanned Air Vehicle (UAV) will fly 6 sorties (The period the UAV is in the air) over the course of the week, with an average of 4 serials (A planned sequence of events) per sortie. The trials management team will be heading to the base on the 24th of March and the Algorithms team will be joining them on April 4th after the trials team have had some time to get the equipment sorted out. The Algorithms team will need to liaise with the trials management team at around 0800 to begin regression testing the Software. They will bring the required platform parameters executable. The engagements we are most interested in are ones where the UAV is evading engagement (moving away from hostile threat); if any of these are not captured there could be some serious development repercussions.

The trials management team will require the Product Integration and Installation Plan (PIIPs) documentation before the 23rd of March so they can take it on to the base. This will need to be collected as it's too sensitive to put through the post. The executives will be on site on April 5th taking the customer through the new improvements, so could everyone onsite be welcoming and professional. This is all depending on the prevailing winds from the SW (South West), which if too strong could see engagements postponed till the following week.

Business Vocabulary Checker Test

* Required

Questions 2b

In the text, what requires regression testing *

- The UAV
- The Software
- The Formula
- The Sortie

Who / What will be on site on the 5th of April *

- The Executive
- The UAV Executable
- The Trials Team
- The Regression Tester

What type of sortie is of most interest *

- Non-hostile sorties
- Approaching targets that are evading engagement
- Flight Sorties
- Moving away from Hostile threats

What does PIIPs stand for *

- Power Isolation and Insulation products
- Performance Isolation and Integrity Partner
- Product Integration and Installation Plan
- Practical installation and Integration Product

Business Vocabulary Checker Test

Text Passage 3b

Read the following passage of text then click next

Over the next few weeks disruption of the intranet, internet and email system may be experienced. There should be no disruption to the Voice over IP (Internet Telephone System) system.

The root cause of this is the reset of the Active Directory (Users and Access Manager) server due to an influx of new users over the past month. The machines next to the IT area on floor 2 provide a bridge (Connection between two networks) to the Oxford office Local Area Network (LAN) should you need to connect to the internet urgently. In addition to the Active Directory server being reset the network switches (Connects segments of the computer network) are being upgraded to accept a high throughput rate. This should reduce the bottlenecking (point at which the flow of data is most highly restricted) effect that the current system is presenting users. Efforts are being made to reduce the disruption to the email service which is additionally affected by the upgrading of the Message Transfer Agent (MTA) software which will stop the outgoing Simple Mail Transfer Protocol (SMTP) server from working from 10pm on the 17th of February for roughly 6 hours. The Intranet should remain least effected as it does not require the Active Directory server for user authentication. You may however experience problems connecting to external resources that are linked to from the intranet. It may also be an issue to connect to the intranet via Virtual Private Network (VPN – used to connect from home computers) from your home laptop.

As always every effort will be made to reduce the disturbances. We appreciate your corporation during this time of change.

Business Vocabulary Checker Test

* Required

Questions 3b

In the context of the passage what is a network switch *

- Something that allows you to turn off the network
- Something that connect segments of a network
- A computer that manages a network
- A computer that queues packets of data

In the context of the passage what is Bottlenecking *

- The point were the flow of data is most highly restricted
- The event of software crashing
- The part of the network which is the oldest
- The point were the flow of data is least restricted

In the context of the passage what is MTA software *

- Major Traffic Actuator software
- Main Traffic Application software
- Message Transfer Agent Software
- Tracking Application software

In the context of the passage what is VPN *

- Virtual Private Network
- Virtual Personal Network
- Vital Partition Networking
- Vital Persons Notify

Business Vocabulary Checker Test

* Required

Post Test Questions

Was the second instance of each text easier to understand than the first *

- Yes
- No
- Not much in it

What could be done to further improve the clarity of the second instance of each text?
(optional)

Any other comments? (optional)

Appendix B Test Results

Appendix B-1 Full Results Set

Participant		Sales and Marketing - Uncorrected Passage				Engineering - Uncorrected Passage				Information Technology - Corrected Passage				Sales and Marketing - Corrected Passage				Engineering - Corrected Passage				Information Technology - Corrected Passage				Improved?	2nd easier?			
Sex	Age	Study	Work	Q1 (Slang)	Q2 (Acronym)	Q3 (Acronym)	Q4 (Complex)	Q1 (Acronym)	Q2 (Slang)	Q3 (Complex)	Q4 (Complex)	Q1 (Acronym)	Q2 (Complex)	Q3 (Slang)	Q4 (Acronym)	Q1 (Complex)	Q2 (Slang)	Q3 (Acronym)	Q4 (Slang)	Q1 (Complex)	Q2 (Slang)	Q3 (Complex)	Q4 (Acronym)	Q1 (Complex)	Q2 (Slang)	Q3 (Acronym)	Q4 (Acronym)			
Inexperienced Participant																														
Male	20-29			0	0	0	1	1	0	1	0	0	0	1	1	1	0	0	0	0	1	1	0	0	1	0	0	1	Yes	No
Male	20-29			0	0	1	1	0	0	1	0	0	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	0	1	Yes	Yes
Male	20-29			0	0	1	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	1	0	1	1	1	0	0	0	0	1	1	1	1	1	Yes	Yes
Female	20-29			1	0	1	1	1	0	0	1	0	0	0	1	0	1	1	1	0	0	0	1	1	1	1	0	1	Yes	Yes
Female	20-29			1	0	1	1	1	0	0	1	0	0	0	1	0	1	1	1	0	0	0	1	1	1	1	0	1	Yes	Yes
Female	20-29			0	0	0	1	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	1	1	1	0	0	0	0	1	1	1	1	1	Yes	Yes
Female	20-29			0	0	1	1	1	0	0	1	0	0	0	1	1	0	1	1	1	1	1	0	1	1	1	1	1	Yes	Yes
Male	30-39			1	0	1	1	1	1	1	0	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	0	1	1	1	1	0	Same	Yes	
Male	30-39			1	0	1	1	1	0	0	1	0	1	1	1	0	1	1	1	1	0	1	1	1	1	1	0	Yes	Not much in it	
Female	30-39			0	1	1	1	1	0	0	0	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	0	1	1	1	1	1	1	Yes	Yes	
Female	30-39			0	0	1	1	1	0	0	0	0	0	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	0	1	1	1	1	1	1	Yes	Not much in it	
Female	40-49			0	0	1	1	1	0	0	0	0	1	0	1	1	1	1	1	1	0	0	1	1	1	0	1	Yes	Yes	
Female	59+			0	0	1	1	1	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	1	1	1	1	0	1	1	1	1	0	1	Yes	Yes		
Single discipline Education																														
Male	20-	1		0	1	1	1	0	1	0	1	1	0	1	1	1	1	1	1	0	1	1	1	1	1	1	0	Yes	Yes	
Male	20-29	3		0	0	1	1	1	1	0	0	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	0	0	0	0	1	1	1	1	1	Same	Yes	
Female	40-49	1		1	0	1	1	1	0	0	0	0	1	1	0	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	Yes	Yes	
Male	50-59	2		0	1	1	1	1	1	1	0	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	0	1	1	1	1	1	Yes	Yes	
Multidiscipline Education																														
Male	20-	3		0	0	1	1	0	0	1	0	0	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	0	1	1	1	Yes	Yes	
Female	20-	1,3		1	1	0	1	1	0	1	0	0	0	1	0	1	1	1	0	1	1	0	0	1	1	1	1	Yes	Yes	
Male	20-29	2,3		0	1	1	1	1	1	1	0	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	0	1	1	1	1	1	Yes	Yes	
Single discipline industry experience																														
Male	20-	3		0	0	1	0	1	0	0	1	1	0	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	0	1	1	0	1	1	1	Yes	Yes	
Male	20-29	2		1	0	0	1	1	0	0	1	1	0	0	1	1	1	0	1	1	0	1	1	0	1	1	1	Yes	Yes	
Female	20-29	1		0	0	1	1	1	0	0	0	1	1	1	1	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	1	1	0	1	0	No	Yes	
Female	20-29	1		0	0	1	1	1	0	0	0	1	1	0	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	Yes	Yes	
Male	40-49	1		1	0	1	1	1	0	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	0	0	1	1	1	1	Same	Not much in it	
Female	50-59	1		1	1	1	1	1	0	0	0	1	1	0	1	1	1	1	1	0	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	Yes	Yes	
Female	59+	2		0	0	1	1	1	0	1	0	1	0	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	0	1	1	1	1	Yes	Yes	
multidiscipline industry																														
Male	20-29	1,3		1	0	1	0	1	0	0	1	1	0	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	0	1	1	0	1	1	1	Yes	Yes	
Female	20-29	1,2		1	1	0	1	1	0	1	1	0	0	1	1	0	1	1	0	1	1	1	0	1	0	0	1	No	Yes	
Male	40-49	2,3		0	0	0	1	1	0	1	1	0	1	0	1	0	1	0	1	1	0	1	1	1	1	1	1	Yes	Yes	
Male	50-59	1,2		0	0	1	1	1	0	1	1	0	1	1	1	0	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	Yes	Yes	
Single discipline education and experience																														
Male	20-29	3	3	0	0	1	1	1	1	0	0	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	0	0	0	0	1	1	1	1	1	Same	Yes	
Male	30-39	2	1	0	1	1	1	0	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	Yes	Yes	
Female	40-49	1	1	1	0	1	1	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	1	0	1	1	0	1	1	1	1	1	0	1	1	Yes	Yes	
Female	40-49	2	2	0	1	1	1	1	1	0	1	1	0	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	0	1	1	1	1	1	1	Yes	Yes	
Female	40-49	3	3	0	0	1	1	1	1	1	0	1	1	0	1	1	1	1	0	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	Yes	Yes	
Male	59+	2	2	0	1	1	1	1	1	1	0	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	0	0	1	1	1	1	1	Same	Yes	
Multi discipline education and experience																														
Male	20-29	1	1,3	0	0	1	0	1	0	0	1	1	0	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	0	1	1	1	0	1	1	Yes	Yes	
Male	20-29	2,3	2,3	1	0	1	1	1	1	0	1	1	1	1	1	0	1	1	0	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	Same	Yes	
Male	20-29	2,3	2,3	1	0	1	0	1	1	1	0	1	0	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	0	1	0	1	1	1	1	Yes	Yes	
Female	20-29	1,3	1	1	1	1	1	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	1	0	1	1	1	0	1	0	1	1	0	0	Yes	Not much in it	
Female	20-29	1,2	1,2	1	1	0	1	1	1	0	1	1	0	0	1	1	1	1	0	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	Yes	Yes	
Male	30-39	1,3	1,3	1	0	1	1	1	1	0	0	0	0	1	1	1	0	1	1	1	0	0	1	0	1	0	1	Same	Yes	
Female	30-39	2,3	2,3	1	1	1	0	0	0	0	1	1	1	1	1	0	1	1	1	1	0	0	1	0	1	0	1	Same	Yes	
Male	40-49	1,3	1,3	1	0	1	1	1	0	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	0	0	1	1	1	1	1	Same	Yes	
Male	50-59	2,3	2,3	1	0	0	1	1	0	1	1	1	1	1	1	0	1	1	0	0	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	Same	Not much in it	
Male	50-59	2	1,2	1	0	1	1	1	0	1	1	0	1	1	1	1	1	0	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	Yes	Yes	
Female	50-59	2,3	1,3	1	0	1	1	1	1	1	0	0	0	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	Yes	Yes	
Male	59+	2	2,3	1	0	1	1	1	1	0	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	0	1	1	1	1	1	Yes	Yes	

Key	
1	Sales and Marketing
2	Engineering
3	Information Technology

Appendix B-2 All Comments Received (with scores)

Participant			Sales and Marketing - Uncorrected Passage				Engineering - Uncorrected Passage				Information Technology - Corrected Passage				Sales and Marketing - Corrected Passage				Engineering - Corrected Passage				Information Technology - Corrected Passage				Comments					
Sex	Age	Study Work	Q1	Q2	Q3	Q4	Q1	Q2	Q3	Q4	Q1	Q2	Q3	Q4	Score1	Q1	Q2	Q3	Q4	Q1	Q2	Q3	Q4	Q1	Q2	Q3	Q4	Score2	Improved?	2nd easier?	What could be done to further improve the clarity of the second instance of each text?	Any other comments?
Female	20-29		1	0	1	1	0	0	1	0	1	0	0	1	6	1	1	0	1	1	1	0	1	1	1	1	1	10	1	Yes		The first set will likely be clearer to current employees at whom it is aimed, and as such may not need adapting. If sent to a wider audience / new staff etc then the expanded version would be needed.
Male	30-39		1	0	1	1	1	0	0	1	0	1	1	1	8	0	1	1	1	1	0	1	1	1	1	1	0	9	1	Not much in it	More concise	The way the test is set up, there was a tendency to skim read second one as 'already read it'
Female	30-39		0	1	1	1	1	0	0	0	1	1	1	1	8	1	1	1	1	1	0	1	1	1	1	1	1	11	1	Yes	The spacing of the text, as even where jargon is explained it became difficult to take in what was being read.	Some of this may be down to context - if the person reading this is working in that area, I'd wonder if they would perhaps feel patronised by having all of the terms explained to them.
Female	30-39		0	0	1	1	0	0	0	0	0	1	1	1	5	0	1	1	1	1	0	1	1	1	1	1	1	10	1	Not much in it	explanation of abbreviations ie LAN (.....meaning)	
Male	40-49	1,3 1,3	1	0	1	1	1	0	1	1	1	1	1	1	10	1	1	1	1	1	0	0	1	1	1	1	1	10	0	Yes	Attached Glossary	
Female	40-49	2 2	0	1	1	1	1	1	0	1	1	0	1	1	9	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	12	1	Yes	Remove acronyms if not required further in the text therefore less to read.	
Male	59+	2 2	0	1	1	1	1	1	1	0	1	1	1	1	10	1	1	1	1	1	1	0	1	1	1	1	1	11	1	Yes	Maybe there could be summary lists of points for each type of 'user' or part of message at the end as a kind of simple re-iteration, which is easily scanned by eye	
Male	59+	2 2,3	1	0	1	1	1	0	1	1	1	1	1	1	10	1	1	1	1	1	1	0	1	1	1	1	1	11	1	Yes	Shorter paragraphs.	Can I see the results of the survey?

Key	
1	Sales and Marketing
2	Engineering
3	Information Technology

Figure 42 Test Results for Participants that made additional comments

Appendix C Prototype System – Screenshots

Appendix C-1 Index.html

Figure 49 index.html - the default home page.

Appendix C-2 termFinder.jsp

The screenshot shows a web browser window with the URL `www.owl-bva.appspot.com/processTerm.jsp`. The page has a navigation bar with links for `Home`, `Look up Term`, and `Analyse Text`. Below the navigation bar is a crest logo. The main content area displays the text `CS5600`, `Prototype Implementation`, and `Term Finder`. A paragraph explains the tool's function: "The Term Finder looks for exact textual matches in the ontology. It does not return partial matches or rank returned terms in best match order. As discussed in the main dissertation document these things have been identified as future enhancements. to analyse a passage of text look on the analyse text page". Below this is a form with a text input field labeled "Please Input Term:", a dropdown menu labeled "Please Select Department Name:" with "Information Technology Vocabulary" selected, and an "Analyse Term" button. The results section, titled "Result Set 1 for VOIP", contains a table with the following data:

Form Type	Form Value
Singular Form	voice over internet protocol
Singular Form	voice over ip
Acronym	voip
Explanation	A voice communication system that uses IP to transfer information, provides similar functionality to a traditional phone system

Below the table, there are sections for "Example Terms" under "Information Technology:" (listing `VOIP`, `active directory`, `bridge`) and "Engineering:".

Figure 50 termFinder.jsp - the basic exact word finder

Appendix C-3 analyseText.jsp

The screenshot shows a web browser window with the URL `www.owl-bva.appspot.com/analyseText.jsp`. The page has a dark blue navigation bar with links for `Home`, `Look up Term`, and `Analyse Text`. Below the navigation bar is a crest logo. The main content area is titled `CS6600` and `Prototype Implementation`, with a subtitle `Text Passage Analyser`. A paragraph explains the tool's function: "The Text Analyser sends a passage of text to the server to check if it contains any terms that are present in the ontology. Cut and paste a desired section of text from the example passage below into the text area and select the relevant department. Press analyse and wait for results." Below this is a form with a dropdown menu for "Please Select Department Name:" set to "Information Technology Vocabulary". A text area for "Please Input Text Passage for Analysis:" contains a sample passage about network issues. Below the text area, it states "In order to limit server load, the amount of text you can pass is limited." and shows a counter for "699 characters left". An "Analyse Text" button is positioned below the counter. At the bottom, there is a section for "Example Passages" with a note: "The example are the uncorrected passages from the test exercise carried out to meet objective one." and a partially visible "Information Technology" label.

Figure 51 analyseText.jsp - the full text analysis request page

Appendix C-4 analysedText.jsp

over the next few weeks disruption of the intranet, internet and email system may be experienced. there should be no disruption to the [vpn](#) system. the route cause of this is the reset of the [active directory](#) server due it an influx of new users over the past month. the machines next to the it area on floor 2 provide a [bridge](#) to the oxford office [lan](#) should you need to connect to the internet urgently. in addition to the [active directory](#) server being reset the [network switches](#) are being upgraded to accept a high throughput rate. this should reduce the [bottlenecking](#) effect that the current system is presenting users. efforts are being made to reduce the disruption to the email service which is additionally affected by the upgrading of the [mta software](#) which will stop the outgoing [smtp](#) server from working from 10pm on the 17th of february for roughly 6 hours. the intranet should remain least effected as it does not require the [active directory](#) server for user authentication. you may however experience problems connecting to external resources that [are linked to from the intranet](#). it may also be an issue to connect to the intranet via [vpn](#) from your home laptop. as [active directory](#) de to reduce the disturbances. we appreciate your corporation his time of change.

Singular Form:
[active directory](#)
Plural Form:
[active directories](#)
Acronym Form:
[ad](#)
Explanation:
[Active Directory](#) is a users and access manager for computer networks

en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Active_Directory

Figure 52 analysedText.jsp - the full text analysis response

Appendix D Ontology – Screenshots

Appendix D-1 BVA.owl

Figure 43 BVA Ontology Class Structure

Figure 44 BVA Ontology Object Property Hierarchy

Figure 45 BVA Ontology Data Property Hierarchy

Appendix D-2 TermAnalyser.owl

Figure 46 Term Analyser Ontology Class Structure

Figure 47 Term Analyser Ontology Data Property Hierarchy

Appendix D-3 TermTester.owl

Figure 48 Term Tester Ontology Class Structure

Appendix E Prototype System – Code

Appendix E-1 Index.html

```
<!DOCTYPE html PUBLIC "-//W3C//DTD HTML 4.01//EN" "http://www.w3.org/TR/html4/strict.dtd">
<!-- this is the default home page for the system, to introduce the functionality that has been
covered -->
<html><head>
  <title>Dissertation - Home</title>
  <link rel="stylesheet" href="/css/screen.css" type="text/css" media="screen, projection">
  <link rel="stylesheet" href="/css/custom.css" type="text/css" media="screen, projection">
  <link rel="stylesheet" href="/css/header.css" type="text/css" media="screen, projection">
</head>
  <body>
    <center>

      <div class="span-4">&nbsp;   </div>
      <div class="span-16 Last">
        <div id="col1">
          <div id="clearer">
            <div class="container">
              <ul class="nav">
                <li><a href="/index.html">Home</a></li>
                <li><a href="/termFinder.jsp">Look up Term</a></li>
                <li><a href="/analyseText.jsp">Analyse Text</a></li>
              </ul>
            </div>
          </div>
        </div>
      </div>

      <hr class="hr10">
      
      <center>
        <hr>
        <h4>CS5500</h4>
        <h3>Dissertation</h3>
        <h4>The Architecture, Design and Justification of an Ontology Based Business
Vocabulary Assistant</h4>
        <hr>

        <table style="width:400px;">
          <tr><th width="100">Student Number</th><th
width="300">Student Name</th></tr>
          <tr><td>0937368</td><td>Steven Hart</td></tr>
        </table>

        <p>The Prototype system demonstrated here is to intended to assist with the
understanding of the architecture, design and ontology
laved out in the dissertation core document. It would be important to note the
dissertation is primarily a architecture, design and ontology and the
implementation is a minor element, utilised only to assist with understanding the
limitations of the OWL-API, Pellet Reasoner and JSP client / server implementation
</p>
        <p>Use the navigation bar along the top of the page to navigate the site. Look up
term allows a user to determine if a term is in the ontology and if so
what information is stored about it. The analyse text page allows a user to pass a
passage of text to the server to determine if any terms that are
in the ontology exist within it.
</p>

      </center>
    </div>
  </center>
</body>
</html>
```

Appendix E-2 termFinder.jsp

```
<%--
  This is the JSP page to allow the user to request term analysis
  Created on : 12-Aug-2011, 16:39:32
  Author    : Steve
--%>
<jsp:useBean id="formHandler" class="bva.server.TermHandler" scope="request"/>

<html xmlns="http://www.w3.org/1999/xhtml">
  <head>
    <meta http-equiv="Content-Type" content="text/html; charset=utf-8" />
    <title>Dissertation - Prototype Implementation</title>
    <link rel="stylesheet" href="/css/screen.css" type="text/css" media="screen, projection" />
    <link rel="stylesheet" href="/css/custom.css" type="text/css" media="screen, projection" />
    <link rel="stylesheet" href="/css/header.css" type="text/css" media="screen, projection" />
  </head>
  <body>
    <div class="span-4">&nbsp;   </div>
    <div class="span-16 Last">
      <div id="col1">
        <div id="clearer">
          <div class="container">
            <ul class="nav">
              <li><a href="/index.html">Home</a></li>
              <li><a href="/termFinder.jsp">Look up Term</a></li>
              <li><a href="/analyseText.jsp">Analyse Text</a></li>
            </ul>
          </div>
        </div>
      </div>
      <div class="hr10" />
      <center>
        
        <hr />
        <h4>CS5500</h4>
        <h3>Prototype Implementation</h3>
        <h4>Term Finder</h4>
        <hr />
        <br />
        <p>The Term Finder looks for exact textual matches in the ontology. It does
not return partial matches or rank returned terms in best match order.
As discussed in the main dissertation document these things have been
identified as future enhancements. to analyse a passage of text look on
the analyse text page</p>
        <hr />
        <form action="processTerm.jsp" method=post>
          <th width="40%" class="style1" scope="col"><div align="left" class="style10">
            <span style="font-weight: 400"><label for="complexTerm">Please Input Term:</label></span>
          </div></th>
          <th width="60%" class="style1" scope="col"><div align="left" class="style10">
            <input name="complexTerm" type="text" size="35" maxlength="50" />
          </div></th>
          <th width="40%" class="style1" scope="col"><div align="left" class="style10">
            <span style="font-weight: 400"><label for="departmentName">Please Select Department
Name:</label></span>
          </div></th>
          <th width="60%" class="style1" scope="col"><div align="left" class="style10">
            <select name="departmentName">
              <option value="#InformationTechnologyTerm">Information Technology Vocabulary</option>
              <option value="#EngineeringTerm">Engineering Vocabulary</option>
              <option value="#SalesMarketingTerm">Sales and Marketing Vocabulary</option>
            </select>
          </div></th>
          <div align="left" class="style10">
            <label for="analyse"></label>
            <input type="submit" value="Analyse Term"/>
          </div>
        </form>
      </p></p>
    </div>
  </body>
</html>
```

```
        <%=formHandler.getReturnMsg("complexTerm")%>
    </center>
<p></p>
<p>Example Terms</p>
<p><b>Information Technology:</b>
<br />VOIP
<br />active directory
<br />bridge</p>

<p><b>Engineering:</b>
<br />UAV
<br />evading engagement
<br />algo</p>

<p><b>Sales and Marketing:</b>
<br />PSS
<br />canvassing
<br />exec</p>

</div>
</body>
</html>
```

Appendix E-3 processTerm.jsp

```
<%--
  This handles the requesting of terms to be analysed
  Created on : 12-Aug-2011, 18:23:43
  Author      : Steve
--%>

<%@ page language="java" %>
<%@ page import="java.util.*" %>
<%!
%>
<jsp:useBean id="formHandler" class="bva.server.TermHandler" scope="request">
<jsp:setProperty name="formHandler" property="*" />
</jsp:useBean>
<%
formHandler.validate(request);
%>
<jsp:forward page="termFinder.jsp" />
```

Appendix E-4 TermHandler.java

```
/**
 * The following Java Class handles terms input by the user into the term finder, passing values
 * to
 * the termAnalysis class which queries the ontology. It handles the user not passing anything and
 * instances
 * where there is no entry in the ontology for the passed term.
 *
 * Author: Steve Hart
 * Date: 16/08/2011
 */

package bva.server;

import java.io.*;
import java.util.*;

import javax.servlet.http.HttpServlet;
import javax.servlet.http.HttpServletRequest;

public class TermHandler extends HttpServlet {

    private static final long serialVersionUID = 1L;

    private String complexTerm;
    private String departmentName;
    private Hashtable results;

    public String resultsString;

    public void validate(HttpServletRequest request) throws IOException {

        // get the parameters from the client side
        complexTerm = request.getParameter("complexTerm");
        departmentName = request.getParameter("departmentName");
        resultsString = "";

        // do some input checking on the user passed values
        if (complexTerm.equals("")) {
            results.put("complexTerm","Please enter a term to analyse");
        }
        else {
            ArrayList termResults = TermAnalysis.getTermResults(complexTerm, departmentName);

            if (termResults != null){

                int i = 0;
                int j = 0;
                int p = 1;

                // build the results table (Future Enhancement, use XML)
                for(i = 0; i < termResults.size();i = i + 2, p++){

                    resultsString = resultsString + "<h4> Result Set " + (p) + " for " +
                    complexTerm + "</h4> <br /> <table style=\"width:400px;\">";
                    resultsString = resultsString + "<tr><th width=\"100\">Form Type</th><th
                    width=\"300\">Form Value</th></tr>";
                    for(j = 0; j < ((ArrayList)termResults.get(i)).size(); j++){
                        resultsString = resultsString + "<tr><td>" +
                        ((String)((ArrayList)termResults.get(i)).get(j)) + "</td><td>" +
                        ((String)((ArrayList)termResults.get(i + 1)).get(j)) + "</td></tr>";
                    }

                    resultsString = resultsString + "</table> <br />";
                }
                results.put("complexTerm",resultsString);
            }
            // handle no value in the ontology terms
        }
    }
}
```

```

        else {
            results.put("complexTerm","There is no term by that name in the ontology");
        }
    }
}

public String getReturnMsg(String s) {

    String returnMsg = (String)results.get(s.trim());
    return (returnMsg == null) ? "":returnMsg;
}

public TermHandler() {

    complexTerm = "";
    departmentName = "";
    results = new Hashtable();
}

public String getTerm() {
    return complexTerm;
}

public String getDepartment() {
    return departmentName;
}

public void setTerm(String te) {
    complexTerm = te;
}

public void setDepartment(String de) {
    departmentName = de;
}

public void setResults(String key, String msg) {
    results.put(key,msg);
}
}

```

Appendix E-5 TermAnalysis.java

```
/**
 * The follow class takes terms passed from the term handler and queries the ontology to find the
 * relevant relationships.
 * it then passes the values back to the handler to organise into a table.
 *
 * Author: Steve Hart
 * Date: 17/08/2011
 */

package bva.server;

import java.io.File;
import java.io.IOException;
import org.semanticweb.owlapi.apibinding.OWLManager;
import org.semanticweb.owlapi.model.*;
import org.semanticweb.owlapi.reasoner.*;

import com.clarkparsia.pellet.owlapiv3.PelletReasoner;
import com.clarkparsia.pellet.owlapiv3.PelletReasonerFactory;
import java.util.ArrayList;

import java.util.Set;
import org.semanticweb.owlapi.util.SimpleIRIMapper;

public class TermAnalysis {

    // declare the ontologies IRI so it can be loaded
    public static final String BVA_IRI = "http://owl-bva.appspot.com/BVA.owl";

    public static ArrayList getTermResults(String term, String department) throws IOException {

        // initialise the ArrayList and convert the passed terms to lowercase
        ArrayList termDetails = new ArrayList();
        term = term.toLowerCase();
        term = term.trim();

        try {

            // use OWLOntologyManager to create the ontology manager
            OWLOntologyManager manager = OWLManager.createOWLOntologyManager();

            // Load the ontology from the document location defined above
            OWLOntology BVA = manager.loadOntologyFromOntologyDocument(IRI.create(BVA_IRI));

            // load and prepare the reasoner
            PelletReasoner reasoner = PelletReasonerFactory.getInstance().createReasoner(BVA);
            reasoner.getKB().realize();

            // Check the ontology is consistent (this is not currently used in the prototype)
            /** boolean consistent = reasoner.isConsistent(); */

            //initiate a owl data factory to manage the passing of objects back from the ontology
            OWLDataFactory fac = manager.getOWLDataFactory();

            // retrieve the data properties from the ontology using the data factory
            OWLDataProperty hasLig = fac.getOWLDataProperty(IRI.create(BVA_IRI +
"#hasLinguistics"));
            OWLDataProperty hasSin = fac.getOWLDataProperty(IRI.create(BVA_IRI + "#hasSingular"));
            OWLDataProperty hasGer = fac.getOWLDataProperty(IRI.create(BVA_IRI + "#hasGerund"));
            OWLDataProperty hasPlu = fac.getOWLDataProperty(IRI.create(BVA_IRI + "#hasPlural"));
            OWLDataProperty hasAcr = fac.getOWLDataProperty(IRI.create(BVA_IRI + "#hasAcronym"));
            OWLDataProperty hasIll = fac.getOWLDataProperty(IRI.create(BVA_IRI +
"#hasIllegalAbbreviation"));
            OWLDataProperty hasExp = fac.getOWLDataProperty(IRI.create(BVA_IRI +
"#hasExplanation"));

            // retrieve the terms from the relevant department
            OWLClass terms = fac.getOWLClass(IRI.create(BVA_IRI + department));
```


Appendix E-6 analyseText.jsp

```
<!--
  This JSP page allows a user to input a passage of text for the system to analyse. it includes
  example passages for the user
  to use to test the current prototype ontology.
  Created on : 12-Aug-2011, 16:39:32
  Author    : Steve
--%>

<html>
  <head>
    <script language="javascript" type="text/javascript">
      function limitText(limitField, limitCount, limitNum) {
        if (limitField.value.length > limitNum) {
          limitField.value = limitField.value.substring(0, limitNum);
        } else {
          limitCount.value = limitNum - limitField.value.length;
        }
      }
    </script>
    <title>Dissertation - Prototype Implementation</title>
    <link rel="stylesheet" href="/css/screen.css" type="text/css" media="screen, projection">
    <link rel="stylesheet" href="/css/custom.css" type="text/css" media="screen, projection">
    <link rel="stylesheet" href="/css/header.css" type="text/css" media="screen, projection">
    <style type="text/css">
      .textAnalysisBox { width: 254px; height: 200px; }
    </style>
  </head>
  <body>
    <div class="span-4">&nbsp;  </div>
    <div class="span-16 Last">
      <div id="col1">
        <div id="clearer">
          <div class="container">
            <ul class="nav">
              <li><a href="/index.html">Home</a></li>
              <li><a href="/termFinder.jsp">Look up Term</a></li>
              <li><a href="/analyseText.jsp">Analyse Text</a></li>
            </ul>
          </div>
        </div>
      </div>
    </div>
    <hr class="hr10">
    <center>
      
      <hr />
      <h4>CS5500</h4>
      <h3>Prototype Implementation</h3>
      <h4>Text Passage Analyser</h4>
      <hr />
      <br/>
      <p>The Text Analyser sends a passage of text to the server to check if it
      contains any terms that are present in the ontology. Cut and paste
      a desired section of text from the example passage below into the text
      area and select the relevant department. Press analyse and wait for results.
      </p>
      <hr />
      <form method="post" action="processText.jsp">
        <th width="40%" class="style1" scope="col"><div align="left" class="style10">
          <span style="font-weight: 400"><label for="departmentName">Please Select Department
        </div></th>
        <th width="60%" class="style1" scope="col"><div align="left" class="style10">
          <select name="departmentName">
            <option value="#InformationTechnologyTerm">Information Technology Vocabulary</option>
            <option value="#EngineeringTerm">Engineering Vocabulary</option>
            <option value="#SalesMarketingTerm">Sales and Marketing Vocabulary</option>
          </select>
        </div></th>
        <th width="40%" class="style1" scope="col"><div align="left" class="style10">
```

```

        <span style="font-weight: 400"><label for="analysisText">Please Input Text Passage for
Analysis:</label></span>
    </div></th>
    <th width="100%" class="style1" scope="col"><div align="left" class="style10">
        <TEXTAREA name="analysisText" rows="20" cols="100"
onKeyDown="limitText(this.form.analysisText,this.form.countdown,2000);"
onKeyUp="limitText(this.form.analysisText,this.form.countdown,2000);"></TEXTAREA>
        <p>In order to limit server load, the amount of text you can pass is limited. <br />
        <input readonly type="text" name="countdown" size="3" value="2000"> characters left.</p>
    </div> </th>

    <td class="style1">
        <div align="left" class="style10">
            <label for="analyse"></label>
            <input type="submit" name="analyse" id="analyse" value="Analyse Text"/>
        </div>

        <th width="60%" class="style1" scope="col"><div align="left" class="style10">
        <br>
            </div></th>

    </form>
<hr />

```

Example Passages

The example are the uncorrected passages from the test exercise carried out to meet objective one.

Information Technology

Over the next few weeks disruption of the intranet, internet and email system may be experienced. There should be no disruption to the VoIP system.

The route cause of this is the reset of the Active Directory server due it an influx of new users over the past month. The machines next to the IT area on floor 2 provide a bridge to the Oxford office LAN should you need to connect to the internet urgently. In addition to the Active Directory server being reset the network switches are being upgraded to accept a high throughput rate. This should reduce the bottlenecking effect that the current system is presenting users. Efforts are being made to reduce the disruption to the email service which is additionally affected by the upgrading of the MTA software which will stop the outgoing SMTP server from working from 10pm on the 17th of February for roughly 6 hours. The Intranet should remain least effected as it does not require the Active Directory server for user authentication. You may however experience problems connecting to external resources that are linked to from the intranet. It may also be an issue to connect to the intranet via VPN from your home laptop.

As always every effort will be made to reduce the disturbances. We appreciate your corporation during this time of change.

Engineering

The UAV will fly 6 sorties over the course of the week, with an average of 4 serials per sortie. The trials management team will be heading to the base on the 24th of March and the Algo team will be joining them on April 4th after the trials team have had some time to get the equipment sorted out. The Algo team will need to liaise with the trials management team at around 0800 to begin regression testing the software. They will bring the required platform parameters executable. The engagements we are most interested in are ones where the UAV is evading engagement; if any of these are not captured there could be some serious development repercussions.

The trials management team will require the PIIPs documentation before the 23rd of March so they can take it on to the base. This will need to be collected as it's too sensitive to put through the post. The exec will be on site on April 5th taking the customer through the new improvements, so could everyone onsite be welcoming and professional. This is all depending on the prevailing winds from the SW, which if too strong could see engagements postponed till the following week.

Sales and Marketing

The following report has been produced for the benefit of the in-house stakeholders of the AWP-66 programme. It is the responsibility of Department managers to circulate this as required.

The company saw an uptake of interest in tangible products steadily during the first quarter; this is mainly regarded as a result of the increased PSS training expenditure and the appointment of Gary Fox as head of discipline. These events have helped increase interest in the AWP-66 programme. This is good news, especially because of the looming funding crisis its up against. It has already been suggested that reduced need for canvassing and AAP expenditure could save up the programme up to 20%. However, it has not reduced the expenditure needed to improve B2B sales. As per predictions during the last quarter of 2010 lead-time is up 8% due to disruptions during the holiday season. This is expected to fall back to mid 2010 levels for Q2; which will bring it back

on track with the yearly target. It's a positive start to the sales year and should continue to increase as the expected order intake is met. Let me take this opportunity to thank all of those that have put so much in to make it a successful first quarter.

```

</p></center></div>
</body>
</html>

```

Appendix E-7 analysedText.jsp

```

<%--
  the following jsp page returns the analysed text to the user after the server side code has
  queried
  Created on : 12-Aug-2011, 16:39:32
  Authors    : Steve, JavaScript curtsey of:
  Capper, 2005. popup hover box [online] <www.ralpharama.co.uk>. accessed on 15/08/2011
--%>

<jsp:useBean id="formHandler" class="bva.server.TextHandler" scope="request"/>

<html xmlns="http://www.w3.org/1999/xhtml">
  <head>
    <script language="javascript">
      <!--
      // ** Popup hover box (c)2005 by Ralph Capper
      // ** www.ralpharama.co.uk
      // ** The follow javascript has been autorised and adapted for use in this project but is not the
      project authors original work.

      // Start trapping mouse

      if (document.layers) document.captureEvents(Event.MOUSEMOVE);
      document.onmousemove=mtrack;
      var ent; // Our floating div
      var posx=0; // Our mouseX
      var posy=0; // Our mouseY
      var offsetX=16; // Offset X away from mouse
      var offsetY=16; // Offset Y
      var popUp = false; // Is it showing right now??!

      // Run upon load
      function init() {
        // Set up div we will use to hover our text
        ent = document.createElement("div");
        // Change these to customise your popup
        ent.style.color = "#06c";
        ent.style.font = "normal 11px Helvetica";
        ent.style.padding = "3px 3px 3px 3px";
        ent.style.background = "#ffffff";
        ent.style.border = "1px solid #06c";
        // Don't, however, change these
        ent.style.left = -100;
        ent.style.top = -100;
        ent.style.position = 'absolute';
        ent.innerHTML = '';
        ent.style.zIndex = 10;
        document.getElementById("thepage").appendChild(ent);
      }
      // Keeps mouse x and y in posx and posy
      function mtrack(e) {
        if (popUp) {
          if (!e) var e = window.event;
          if (e.pageX || e.pageY) {
            posx = e.pageX;
            posy = e.pageY;
          }
          else if (e.clientX || e.clientY) {
            posx = e.clientX + document.body.scrollLeft;
            posy = e.clientY + document.body.scrollTop;
          }
          ent.style.left = posx + offsetX;
          ent.style.top = posy + offsetY;

```

```

}
}
// Change floating div to correct text on mouseover
function doText(t, e) {
popUp = true;
ent.innerHTML = t;
}
// Change back to nothing
function doClear() {
popUp = false;
ent.style.left = -100;
ent.style.top = -100;
ent.innerHTML = "";
}
-->
</script>

<meta http-equiv="Content-Type" content="text/html; charset=utf-8" />
<title>Dissertation - Prototype Implementation</title>
<link rel="stylesheet" href="/css/screen.css" type="text/css" media="screen, projection" />
<link rel="stylesheet" href="/css/custom.css" type="text/css" media="screen, projection" />
<link rel="stylesheet" href="/css/header.css" type="text/css" media="screen, projection" />
</head>

<body>

<div class="span-4">&nbsp;&nbsp;&nbsp;&nbsp;</div>
<div class="span-16 Last">
<div id="col1">
<div id="clearer">
<div class="container">
<ul class="nav">
<li><a href="/index.html">Home</a></li>
<li><a href="/termFinder.jsp">Look up Term</a></li>
<li><a href="/analyseText.jsp">Analyse Text</a></li>
</ul>
</div>
</div>
</div>
</div>
<hr class="hr10" />
<center>

<hr />
<h4>CS5500</h4>
<h3>Prototype Implementation</h3>
<h4>Analysed Text Results</h4>
<hr />
<body onLoad="init();" id="thepage">

<!--get the returned analysed text from the server side -->
<p><%=formHandler.getReturnMsg("analysisText")%></p>

</center>
</div>
</body>
</html>

```

Appendix E-8 processText.jsp

```
<%--
  This handles the requesting of text to be analysed
  Created on : 12-Aug-2011, 18:23:43
  Author    : Steve
--%>

<%@ page language="java" %>
<%@ page import="java.util.*" %>
<%!
%>
<jsp:useBean id="formHandler" class="bva.server.TextHandler" scope="request">
<jsp:setProperty name="formHandler" property="*" />
</jsp:useBean>
<%
formHandler.validate(request);
%>
<jsp:forward page="analysedText.jsp" />
```

Appendix E-9 TextHandler.java

```
/**
 * The following Java Class handles text input by the user into the term finder, passing values to
 * textAnalysis class which queries the ontology. It handles the user not passing anything and
 instances
 * where there is no entry in the ontology for any of the passed text.
 *
 * Author: Steve Hart
 * Date: 20/08/2011
 */
package bva.server;

import java.io.*;
import java.util.*;

import javax.servlet.http.HttpServlet;
import javax.servlet.http.HttpServletRequest;

public class TextHandler extends HttpServlet {

    /**
     *
     */
    private static final long serialVersionUID = 1L;

    private String analysisText;
    private String departmentName;
    private Hashtable results;

    public String resultsString;

    public void validate(HttpServletRequest request) throws IOException {

        // get the parameters from the client side
        analysisText = request.getParameter("analysisText");
        departmentName = request.getParameter("departmentName");
        resultsString = "";

        // do some input checking on the user passed values
        if (analysisText.equals("")) {
            results.put("analysisText", "Please enter some text to analyse");
        }
        else {
            String resultsString = TextAnalysis.getTermResults(analysisText, departmentName);

            if (resultsString != null){

                results.put("analysisText", resultsString);
            }
            // handle no value in the ontology terms
            else {
                results.put("analysisText", "There is no terms in the ontology that are also in the
 analysed text");
            }
        }
    }

    public String getReturnMsg(String s) {

        String returnMsg = (String)results.get(s.trim());
        return (returnMsg == null) ? "" : returnMsg;
    }

    public TextHandler() {

        analysisText = "";
        departmentName = "";
        results = new Hashtable();
    }
    public String getText() {
```

```
        return analysisText;
    }
    public String getDepartment() {
        return departmentName;
    }
    public void setText(String te) {
        analysisText = te;
    }
    public void setDepartment(String de) {
        departmentName = de;
    }
    public void setResults(String key, String msg) {
        results.put(key,msg);
    }
}
```

Appendix E-10 TextAnalysis.java

```
/**
 * The following class builds queries the ontology to find if any terms exist within a passed
 * passage on text. If so the class replaces
 * this with the html into the string. In the future the use of Regex and XML could be used to
 * make this more robust.
 *
 * Author: Steve Hart
 * Date: 21/08/2011
 */

package bva.server;

import java.io.IOException;
import org.semanticweb.owlapi.apibinding.OWLManager;
import org.semanticweb.owlapi.model.*;
import org.semanticweb.owlapi.reasoner.*;

import com.clarkparsia.pellet.owlapiv3.PelletReasoner;
import com.clarkparsia.pellet.owlapiv3.PelletReasonerFactory;

import java.util.Set;

public class TextAnalysis {

    public static final String BVA_IRI = "http://owl-bva.appspot.com/BVA.owl";

    public static String getTermResults(String text, String department) throws IOException {

        String infoText = new String();
        // make text lower case for analysis (Future Enhancement use Regex to avoid doing this)
        text = text.toLowerCase();

        // make sure terms are always proceeded by spaces for comparison below (Future Enhancement use
        // Regex to avoid doing this)
        text = text.replace(".", " ~.");
        text = text.replace(",", " ~,");
        text = text.replace(":", " ~:");
        text = text.replace(";"," ~;");
        text = text.replace("?", " ~?");
        text = text.replace("!", " ~!");
        try {

            // use OWLOntologyManager to create the ontology manager
            OWLOntologyManager manager = OWLManager.createOWLOntologyManager();

            // Load the ontology from the document location defined above
            OWLOntology BVA = manager.loadOntologyFromOntologyDocument(IRI.create(BVA_IRI));

            // load and prepare the reasoner
            PelletReasoner reasoner = PelletReasonerFactory.getInstance().createReasoner(BVA);
            reasoner.getKB().realize();

            // Check the ontology is consistent (this is not currently used in the prototype)
            /** boolean consistent = reasoner.isConsistent(); */

            //initiate a owl data factory to manage the passing of objects back from the ontology
            OWLDataFactory fac = manager.getOWLDataFactory();

            // retrieve the data properties from the ontology using the data factory
            OWLDataProperty hasLig = fac.getOWLDataProperty(IRI.create(BVA_IRI +
            "#hasLinguistics"));
            OWLDataProperty hasSin = fac.getOWLDataProperty(IRI.create(BVA_IRI + "#hasSingular"));
            OWLDataProperty hasGer = fac.getOWLDataProperty(IRI.create(BVA_IRI + "#hasGerund"));
            OWLDataProperty hasPlu = fac.getOWLDataProperty(IRI.create(BVA_IRI + "#hasPlural"));
            OWLDataProperty hasAcr = fac.getOWLDataProperty(IRI.create(BVA_IRI + "#hasAcronym"));
            OWLDataProperty hasIll = fac.getOWLDataProperty(IRI.create(BVA_IRI +
            "#hasIllegalAbbreviation"));
        }
    }
}
```

```

        OWLDataProperty hasExp = fac.getOWLDataProperty(IRI.create(BVA_IRI +
"#hasExplanation"));
        OWLDataProperty hasWeb = fac.getOWLDataProperty(IRI.create(BVA_IRI +
"#hasWebResource"));

        // retrieve the terms from the relevant department
        OWLClass terms = fac.getOWLClass(IRI.create(BVA_IRI + department));

        NodeSet<OWLNamedIndividual> termNodes = reasoner.getInstances(terms, true);

        Set<OWLNamedIndividual> termSet = termNodes.getFlattened();
        for(OWLNamedIndividual ind : termSet) {

            Set<OWLLiteral> literals = reasoner.getDataPropertyValues(ind,hasLig);

            for(OWLLiteral lit: literals){
                // find term instances, must be preceded and proceeded by a space to avoid
                if (text.contains(" "+lit.getLiteral()+" ")){

                    // start building the infotext string (Future Enhancement, use XML)
                    infoText = "<a href=\"";

                    Set<OWLLiteral> litWeb = reasoner.getDataPropertyValues(ind,hasWeb);
                    for(OWLLiteral lw : litWeb){
                        if (lw.getLiteral() != "" && lw.getLiteral() != null ){
                            infoText = infoText + lw.getLiteral() + "\" target=\"_blank\"";
                        }
                    }

                    if (infoText.length() < 11){
                        infoText = infoText + "#\"";
                    }

                    infoText = infoText + " onMouseover=\"doText('";

                    Set<OWLLiteral> litSin = reasoner.getDataPropertyValues(ind,hasSin);
                    for(OWLLiteral ls : litSin){
                        infoText = infoText + "<font color=black>Singular Form:</font><br />";
                        infoText = infoText + ls.getLiteral() + "<br />";
                    }

                    Set<OWLLiteral> litGer = reasoner.getDataPropertyValues(ind,hasGer);
                    for(OWLLiteral la : litGer){
                        infoText = infoText + "<font color=black>Gerund Form:</font><br />";
                        infoText = infoText + la.getLiteral() + "<br />";
                    }

                    Set<OWLLiteral> litPlu = reasoner.getDataPropertyValues(ind,hasPlu);
                    for(OWLLiteral lp : litPlu){
                        infoText = infoText + "<font color=black>Plural Form:</font><br />";
                        infoText = infoText + lp.getLiteral() + "<br />";
                    }

                    Set<OWLLiteral> litAcr = reasoner.getDataPropertyValues(ind,hasAcr);
                    for(OWLLiteral la : litAcr){
                        infoText = infoText + "<font color=black>Acronym Form:</font><br />";
                        infoText = infoText + la.getLiteral() + "<br />";
                    }

                    Set<OWLLiteral> litIll = reasoner.getDataPropertyValues(ind,hasIll);
                    for(OWLLiteral li : litIll){
                        infoText = infoText + "<font color=black>Illegal Form:</font><br />";
                        infoText = infoText + li.getLiteral() + "<br />";
                    }

                    Set<OWLLiteral> litExp = reasoner.getDataPropertyValues(ind,hasExp);
                    for(OWLLiteral el : litExp){

                        // wrap the text to the nearest space to 30 characters long
                        StringBuilder sb = new StringBuilder(el.getLiteral());
                        String expString = "<font color=black>Explanation:</font><br />";
                        int i = 0;
                        while ((i = sb.indexOf(" ", i + 30)) != -1) {
                            sb.replace(i, i + 1, "<br />");
                        }
                    }
                }
            }
        }

```


Appendix E-11 Web.xml – servlet mappings

```
<?xml version="1.0" encoding="UTF-8"?>
<!DOCTYPE web-app
  PUBLIC "-//Sun Microsystems, Inc.//DTD Web Application 2.3//EN"
  "http://java.sun.com/dtd/web-app_2_3.dtd">

<web-app>

  <servlet>
    <servlet-name>TermHandler</servlet-name>
    <servlet-class>bva.server.TermHandler</servlet-class>
  </servlet>

  <servlet>
    <servlet-name>TextHandler</servlet-name>
    <servlet-class>bva.server.TextHandler</servlet-class>
  </servlet>

  <servlet-mapping>
    <servlet-name>TermHandler</servlet-name>
    <url-pattern>/TermHandler</url-pattern>
  </servlet-mapping>

  <servlet-mapping>
    <servlet-name>TextHandler</servlet-name>
    <url-pattern>/TextHandler</url-pattern>
  </servlet-mapping>

  <!-- Default page to serve -->
  <welcome-file-list>
    <welcome-file>index.html</welcome-file>
  </welcome-file-list>

</web-app>
```

Appendix F Ontology – Code

Appendix F-1 BVA.owl

```
<?xml version="1.0"?>

<!DOCTYPE Ontology [
  <!ENTITY xsd "http://www.w3.org/2001/XMLSchema#" >
  <!ENTITY xml "http://www.w3.org/XML/1998/namespace" >
  <!ENTITY rdfs "http://www.w3.org/2000/01/rdf-schema#" >
  <!ENTITY rdf "http://www.w3.org/1999/02/22-rdf-syntax-ns#" >
]>

<Ontology xmlns="http://www.w3.org/2002/07/owl#"
  xml:base="http://owl-bva.appspot.com/BVA.owl"
  xmlns:rdfs="http://www.w3.org/2000/01/rdf-schema#"
  xmlns:xsd="http://www.w3.org/2001/XMLSchema#"
  xmlns:rdf="http://www.w3.org/1999/02/22-rdf-syntax-ns#"
  xmlns:xml="http://www.w3.org/XML/1998/namespace"
  ontologyIRI="http://owl-bva.appspot.com/BVA.owl">
  <Prefix name="xsd" IRI="http://www.w3.org/2001/XMLSchema#"/>
  <Prefix name="owl" IRI="http://www.w3.org/2002/07/owl#"/>
  <Prefix name="owl2xml" IRI="http://www.w3.org/2006/12/owl2-xml#"/>
  <Prefix name="" IRI="http://owl-bva.appspot.com/BVA.owl#"/>
  <Prefix name="rdf" IRI="http://www.w3.org/1999/02/22-rdf-syntax-ns#"/>
  <Prefix name="rdfs" IRI="http://www.w3.org/2000/01/rdf-schema#"/>
  <Import>http://owl-bva.appspot.com/TermAnalyser.owl</Import>
  <Declaration>
    <Class IRI="#EngineeringTerm"/>
  </Declaration>
  <Declaration>
    <Class IRI="#InformationTechnologyTerm"/>
  </Declaration>
  <Declaration>
    <Class IRI="#SalesMarketingTerm"/>
  </Declaration>
  <Declaration>
    <Class IRI="#Term"/>
  </Declaration>
  <Declaration>
    <ObjectProperty IRI="#hasEquivalentTerm"/>
  </Declaration>
  <Declaration>
    <ObjectProperty IRI="#hasPreferredTerm"/>
  </Declaration>
  <Declaration>
    <ObjectProperty IRI="#hasRelatedTerm"/>
  </Declaration>
  <Declaration>
    <DataProperty IRI="#hasAcronym"/>
  </Declaration>
  <Declaration>
    <DataProperty IRI="#hasExplanation"/>
  </Declaration>
  <Declaration>
    <DataProperty IRI="#hasGerund"/>
  </Declaration>
  <Declaration>
    <DataProperty IRI="#hasIllegalAbbreviation"/>
  </Declaration>
  <Declaration>
    <DataProperty IRI="#hasLinguistics"/>
  </Declaration>
  <Declaration>
    <DataProperty IRI="#hasPlural"/>
  </Declaration>
  <Declaration>
    <DataProperty IRI="#hasSingular"/>
  </Declaration>

```

```

<Declaration>
  <DataProperty IRI="#hasWebResource"/>
</Declaration>
<Declaration>
  <NamedIndividual IRI="#term-Active_Directory"/>
</Declaration>
<Declaration>
  <NamedIndividual IRI="#term-Advertising_And_Promotion"/>
</Declaration>
<Declaration>
  <NamedIndividual IRI="#term-Algorithm"/>
</Declaration>
<Declaration>
  <NamedIndividual IRI="#term-Bottleneck"/>
</Declaration>
<Declaration>
  <NamedIndividual IRI="#term-Bridge"/>
</Declaration>
<Declaration>
  <NamedIndividual IRI="#term-Business_To_Business"/>
</Declaration>
<Declaration>
  <NamedIndividual IRI="#term-Canvassing"/>
</Declaration>
<Declaration>
  <NamedIndividual IRI="#term-Cold_Calling"/>
</Declaration>
<Declaration>
  <NamedIndividual IRI="#term-Evading_Engagement"/>
</Declaration>
<Declaration>
  <NamedIndividual IRI="#term-Executive"/>
</Declaration>
<Declaration>
  <NamedIndividual IRI="#term-Lead_Time"/>
</Declaration>
<Declaration>
  <NamedIndividual IRI="#term-Local_Area_Network"/>
</Declaration>
<Declaration>
  <NamedIndividual IRI="#term-Message_Transfer_Agent"/>
</Declaration>
<Declaration>
  <NamedIndividual IRI="#term-Network_Switch"/>
</Declaration>
<Declaration>
  <NamedIndividual IRI="#term-Physical_Products"/>
</Declaration>
<Declaration>
  <NamedIndividual IRI="#term-Product_Integration_and_Installation_Plan"/>
</Declaration>
<Declaration>
  <NamedIndividual IRI="#term-Professional_Sales_Skill"/>
</Declaration>
<Declaration>
  <NamedIndividual IRI="#term-Sales_Target"/>
</Declaration>
<Declaration>
  <NamedIndividual IRI="#term-Second_Quarter"/>
</Declaration>
<Declaration>
  <NamedIndividual IRI="#term-Serial"/>
</Declaration>
<Declaration>
  <NamedIndividual IRI="#term-Simple_Mail_Transfer_Protocol"/>
</Declaration>
<Declaration>
  <NamedIndividual IRI="#term-Software"/>
</Declaration>
<Declaration>
  <NamedIndividual IRI="#term-Sortie"/>
</Declaration>
<Declaration>
  <NamedIndividual IRI="#term-South_West"/>

```

```

</Declaration>
<Declaration>
  <NamedIndividual IRI="#term-Tangible_Asset"/>
</Declaration>
<Declaration>
  <NamedIndividual IRI="#term-Tangible_Product"/>
</Declaration>
<Declaration>
  <NamedIndividual IRI="#term-Unmanned_Air_Vehicle"/>
</Declaration>
<Declaration>
  <NamedIndividual IRI="#term-Virtual_Private_Network"/>
</Declaration>
<Declaration>
  <NamedIndividual IRI="#term-Voice_Over_IP"/>
</Declaration>
<Declaration>
  <NamedIndividual IRI="#term_Target"/>
</Declaration>
<SubClassOf>
  <Class IRI="#EngineeringTerm"/>
  <Class IRI="#Term"/>
</SubClassOf>
<SubClassOf>
  <Class IRI="#InformationTechnologyTerm"/>
  <Class IRI="#Term"/>
</SubClassOf>
<SubClassOf>
  <Class IRI="#SalesMarketingTerm"/>
  <Class IRI="#Term"/>
</SubClassOf>
<ClassAssertion>
  <Class IRI="#InformationTechnologyTerm"/>
  <NamedIndividual IRI="#term-Active_Directory"/>
</ClassAssertion>
<ClassAssertion>
  <Class IRI="#SalesMarketingTerm"/>
  <NamedIndividual IRI="#term-Advertising_And_Promotion"/>
</ClassAssertion>
<ClassAssertion>
  <Class IRI="#EngineeringTerm"/>
  <NamedIndividual IRI="#term-Algorithm"/>
</ClassAssertion>
<ClassAssertion>
  <Class IRI="#InformationTechnologyTerm"/>
  <NamedIndividual IRI="#term-Bottleneck"/>
</ClassAssertion>
<ClassAssertion>
  <Class IRI="#InformationTechnologyTerm"/>
  <NamedIndividual IRI="#term-Bridge"/>
</ClassAssertion>
<ClassAssertion>
  <Class IRI="#SalesMarketingTerm"/>
  <NamedIndividual IRI="#term-Business_To_Business"/>
</ClassAssertion>
<ClassAssertion>
  <Class IRI="#SalesMarketingTerm"/>
  <NamedIndividual IRI="#term-Canvassing"/>
</ClassAssertion>
<ClassAssertion>
  <Class IRI="#SalesMarketingTerm"/>
  <NamedIndividual IRI="#term-Cold_Calling"/>
</ClassAssertion>
<ClassAssertion>
  <Class IRI="#EngineeringTerm"/>
  <NamedIndividual IRI="#term-Evading_Engagement"/>
</ClassAssertion>
<ClassAssertion>
  <Class IRI="#EngineeringTerm"/>
  <NamedIndividual IRI="#term-Executive"/>
</ClassAssertion>
<ClassAssertion>
  <Class IRI="#InformationTechnologyTerm"/>
  <NamedIndividual IRI="#term-Executive"/>

```

```

</ClassAssertion>
<ClassAssertion>
  <Class IRI="#SalesMarketingTerm"/>
  <NamedIndividual IRI="#term-Executive"/>
</ClassAssertion>
<ClassAssertion>
  <Class IRI="#SalesMarketingTerm"/>
  <NamedIndividual IRI="#term-Lead_Time"/>
</ClassAssertion>
<ClassAssertion>
  <Class IRI="#InformationTechnologyTerm"/>
  <NamedIndividual IRI="#term-Local_Area_Network"/>
</ClassAssertion>
<ClassAssertion>
  <Class IRI="#InformationTechnologyTerm"/>
  <NamedIndividual IRI="#term-Message_Transfer_Agent"/>
</ClassAssertion>
<ClassAssertion>
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  <NamedIndividual IRI="#term-Network_Switch"/>
</ClassAssertion>
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  <NamedIndividual IRI="#term-Physical_Products"/>
</ClassAssertion>
<ClassAssertion>
  <Class IRI="#EngineeringTerm"/>
  <NamedIndividual IRI="#term-Product_Integration_and_Installation_Plan"/>
</ClassAssertion>
<ClassAssertion>
  <Class IRI="#SalesMarketingTerm"/>
  <NamedIndividual IRI="#term-Professional_Sales_Skill"/>
</ClassAssertion>
<ClassAssertion>
  <Class IRI="#SalesMarketingTerm"/>
  <NamedIndividual IRI="#term-Sales_Target"/>
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  <Class IRI="#SalesMarketingTerm"/>
  <NamedIndividual IRI="#term-Second_Quarter"/>
</ClassAssertion>
<ClassAssertion>
  <Class IRI="#EngineeringTerm"/>
  <NamedIndividual IRI="#term-Serial"/>
</ClassAssertion>
<ClassAssertion>
  <Class IRI="#InformationTechnologyTerm"/>
  <NamedIndividual IRI="#term-Simple_Mail_Transfer_Protocol"/>
</ClassAssertion>
<ClassAssertion>
  <Class IRI="#EngineeringTerm"/>
  <NamedIndividual IRI="#term-Software"/>
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  <NamedIndividual IRI="#term-Software"/>
</ClassAssertion>
<ClassAssertion>
  <Class IRI="#EngineeringTerm"/>
  <NamedIndividual IRI="#term-Sortie"/>
</ClassAssertion>
<ClassAssertion>
  <Class IRI="#EngineeringTerm"/>
  <NamedIndividual IRI="#term-South_West"/>
</ClassAssertion>
<ClassAssertion>
  <Class IRI="#SalesMarketingTerm"/>
  <NamedIndividual IRI="#term-Tangible_Asset"/>
</ClassAssertion>
<ClassAssertion>
  <Class IRI="#SalesMarketingTerm"/>
  <NamedIndividual IRI="#term-Tangible_Product"/>
</ClassAssertion>
<ClassAssertion>

```

```

    <Class IRI="#EngineeringTerm"/>
    <NamedIndividual IRI="#term-Unmanned_Air_Vehicle"/>
</ClassAssertion>
<ClassAssertion>
    <Class IRI="#InformationTechnologyTerm"/>
    <NamedIndividual IRI="#term-Virtual_Private_Network"/>
</ClassAssertion>
<ClassAssertion>
    <Class IRI="#InformationTechnologyTerm"/>
    <NamedIndividual IRI="#term-Voice_Over_IP"/>
</ClassAssertion>
<ClassAssertion>
    <Class IRI="#SalesMarketingTerm"/>
    <NamedIndividual IRI="#term_Target"/>
</ClassAssertion>
<ObjectPropertyAssertion>
    <ObjectProperty IRI="#hasRelatedTerm"/>
    <NamedIndividual IRI="#term-Bottleneck"/>
    <NamedIndividual IRI="#term-Local_Area_Network"/>
</ObjectPropertyAssertion>
<ObjectPropertyAssertion>
    <ObjectProperty IRI="#hasPreferredTerm"/>
    <NamedIndividual IRI="#term-Canvassing"/>
    <NamedIndividual IRI="#term-Cold_Calling"/>
</ObjectPropertyAssertion>
<ObjectPropertyAssertion>
    <ObjectProperty IRI="#hasRelatedTerm"/>
    <NamedIndividual IRI="#term-Message_Transfer_Agent"/>
    <NamedIndividual IRI="#term-Simple_Mail_Transfer_Protocol"/>
</ObjectPropertyAssertion>
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    <ObjectProperty IRI="#hasEquivalentTerm"/>
    <NamedIndividual IRI="#term-Physical_Products"/>
    <NamedIndividual IRI="#term-Tangible_Product"/>
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    <ObjectProperty IRI="#hasEquivalentTerm"/>
    <NamedIndividual IRI="#term-Physical_Products"/>
    <NamedIndividual IRI="#term-Tangible_Asset"/>
</ObjectPropertyAssertion>
<ObjectPropertyAssertion>
    <ObjectProperty IRI="#hasRelatedTerm"/>
    <NamedIndividual IRI="#term-Sortie"/>
    <NamedIndividual IRI="#term-Serial"/>
</ObjectPropertyAssertion>
<ObjectPropertyAssertion>
    <ObjectProperty IRI="#hasEquivalentTerm"/>
    <NamedIndividual IRI="#term-Tangible_Asset"/>
    <NamedIndividual IRI="#term-Tangible_Product"/>
</ObjectPropertyAssertion>
<ObjectPropertyAssertion>
    <ObjectProperty IRI="#hasPreferredTerm"/>
    <NamedIndividual IRI="#term-Tangible_Asset"/>
    <NamedIndividual IRI="#term-Physical_Products"/>
</ObjectPropertyAssertion>
<ObjectPropertyAssertion>
    <ObjectProperty IRI="#hasPreferredTerm"/>
    <NamedIndividual IRI="#term-Tangible_Product"/>
    <NamedIndividual IRI="#term-Physical_Products"/>
</ObjectPropertyAssertion>
<ObjectPropertyAssertion>
    <ObjectProperty IRI="#hasPreferredTerm"/>
    <NamedIndividual IRI="#term_Target"/>
    <NamedIndividual IRI="#term-Sales_Target"/>
</ObjectPropertyAssertion>
<DataPropertyAssertion>
    <DataProperty IRI="#hasAcronym"/>
    <NamedIndividual IRI="#term-Active_Directory"/>
    <Literal datatypeIRI="#xsd:string">ad</Literal>
</DataPropertyAssertion>
<DataPropertyAssertion>
    <DataProperty IRI="#hasExplanation"/>
    <NamedIndividual IRI="#term-Active_Directory"/>

```

```

    <Literal datatypeIRI="&#x3d;string">Active Directory is a users and access manager for
computer networks</Literal>
  </DataPropertyAssertion>
  <DataPropertyAssertion>
    <DataProperty IRI="#hasPlural"/>
    <NamedIndividual IRI="#term-Active_Directory"/>
    <Literal datatypeIRI="&#x3d;string">active directories</Literal>
  </DataPropertyAssertion>
  <DataPropertyAssertion>
    <DataProperty IRI="#hasSingular"/>
    <NamedIndividual IRI="#term-Active_Directory"/>
    <Literal datatypeIRI="&#x3d;string">active directory</Literal>
  </DataPropertyAssertion>
  <DataPropertyAssertion>
    <DataProperty IRI="#hasWebResource"/>
    <NamedIndividual IRI="#term-Active_Directory"/>
    <Literal datatypeIRI="&#x3d;anyURI">http://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Active_Directory</Literal>
  </DataPropertyAssertion>
  <DataPropertyAssertion>
    <DataProperty IRI="#hasAcronym"/>
    <NamedIndividual IRI="#term-Advertising_And_Promotion"/>
    <Literal datatypeIRI="&#x3d;string">A&#x26;P</Literal>
  </DataPropertyAssertion>
  <DataPropertyAssertion>
    <DataProperty IRI="#hasAcronym"/>
    <NamedIndividual IRI="#term-Advertising_And_Promotion"/>
    <Literal datatypeIRI="&#x3d;string">AAP</Literal>
  </DataPropertyAssertion>
  <DataPropertyAssertion>
    <DataProperty IRI="#hasExplanation"/>
    <NamedIndividual IRI="#term-Advertising_And_Promotion"/>
    <Literal datatypeIRI="&#x3d;string">the use of mass media to present a companies ideas,
goods and services</Literal>
  </DataPropertyAssertion>
  <DataPropertyAssertion>
    <DataProperty IRI="#hasGerund"/>
    <NamedIndividual IRI="#term-Advertising_And_Promotion"/>
    <Literal datatypeIRI="&#x3d;string">advertising and promotion</Literal>
  </DataPropertyAssertion>
  <DataPropertyAssertion>
    <DataProperty IRI="#hasPlural"/>
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  <DataProperty IRI="#hasExplanation"/>
  <NamedIndividual IRI="#term-Voice_Over_IP"/>
  <Literal datatypeIRI="&#xsd;string">A voice communication system that uses IP to transfer
information, provides similar functionality to a traditional phone system</Literal>
</DataPropertyAssertion>
<DataPropertyAssertion>
  <DataProperty IRI="#hasSingular"/>
  <NamedIndividual IRI="#term-Voice_Over_IP"/>
  <Literal datatypeIRI="&#xsd;string">voice over ip</Literal>
</DataPropertyAssertion>
<DataPropertyAssertion>
  <DataProperty IRI="#hasSingular"/>
  <NamedIndividual IRI="#term-Voice_Over_IP"/>
  <Literal datatypeIRI="&#xsd;string">voice over internet protocol</Literal>
</DataPropertyAssertion>
<DataPropertyAssertion>
  <DataProperty IRI="#hasWebResource"/>
  <NamedIndividual IRI="#term-Voice_Over_IP"/>
  <Literal
datatypeIRI="&#xsd;anyURI">http://www.google.co.uk/search?q=voice+over+ip</Literal>
</DataPropertyAssertion>
<DataPropertyAssertion>
  <DataProperty IRI="#hasPlural"/>
  <NamedIndividual IRI="#term_Target"/>
  <Literal datatypeIRI="&#xsd;string">targets</Literal>
</DataPropertyAssertion>
<DataPropertyAssertion>
  <DataProperty IRI="#hasSingular"/>
  <NamedIndividual IRI="#term_Target"/>
  <Literal datatypeIRI="&#xsd;string">target</Literal>
</DataPropertyAssertion>
<SubObjectPropertyOf>
  <ObjectProperty IRI="#hasPreferredTerm"/>
  <ObjectProperty IRI="#hasEquivalentTerm"/>

```

```

</SubObjectPropertyOf>
<SymmetricObjectProperty>
  <ObjectProperty IRI="#hasEquivalentTerm"/>
</SymmetricObjectProperty>
<SymmetricObjectProperty>
  <ObjectProperty IRI="#hasRelatedTerm"/>
</SymmetricObjectProperty>
<ObjectPropertyDomain>
  <ObjectProperty IRI="#hasEquivalentTerm"/>
  <Class IRI="#Term"/>
</ObjectPropertyDomain>
<ObjectPropertyDomain>
  <ObjectProperty IRI="#hasPreferredTerm"/>
  <Class IRI="#Term"/>
</ObjectPropertyDomain>
<ObjectPropertyDomain>
  <ObjectProperty IRI="#hasRelatedTerm"/>
  <Class IRI="#Term"/>
</ObjectPropertyDomain>
<ObjectPropertyRange>
  <ObjectProperty IRI="#hasEquivalentTerm"/>
  <Class IRI="#Term"/>
</ObjectPropertyRange>
<ObjectPropertyRange>
  <ObjectProperty IRI="#hasPreferredTerm"/>
  <Class IRI="#Term"/>
</ObjectPropertyRange>
<ObjectPropertyRange>
  <ObjectProperty IRI="#hasRelatedTerm"/>
  <Class IRI="#Term"/>
</ObjectPropertyRange>
<SubDataPropertyOf>
  <DataProperty IRI="#hasAcronym"/>
  <DataProperty IRI="#hasLinguistics"/>
</SubDataPropertyOf>
<SubDataPropertyOf>
  <DataProperty IRI="#hasExplanation"/>
  <DataProperty abbreviatedIRI="owl:topDataProperty"/>
</SubDataPropertyOf>
<SubDataPropertyOf>
  <DataProperty IRI="#hasGerund"/>
  <DataProperty IRI="#hasLinguistics"/>
</SubDataPropertyOf>
<SubDataPropertyOf>
  <DataProperty IRI="#hasIllegalAbbreviation"/>
  <DataProperty IRI="#hasLinguistics"/>
</SubDataPropertyOf>
<SubDataPropertyOf>
  <DataProperty IRI="#hasPlural"/>
  <DataProperty IRI="#hasLinguistics"/>
</SubDataPropertyOf>
<SubDataPropertyOf>
  <DataProperty IRI="#hasSingular"/>
  <DataProperty IRI="#hasLinguistics"/>
</SubDataPropertyOf>
<DataPropertyDomain>
  <DataProperty IRI="#hasAcronym"/>
  <Class IRI="#Term"/>
</DataPropertyDomain>
<DataPropertyDomain>
  <DataProperty IRI="#hasExplanation"/>
  <Class IRI="#Term"/>
</DataPropertyDomain>
<DataPropertyDomain>
  <DataProperty IRI="#hasGerund"/>
  <Class IRI="#Term"/>
</DataPropertyDomain>
<DataPropertyDomain>
  <DataProperty IRI="#hasIllegalAbbreviation"/>
  <Class IRI="#Term"/>
</DataPropertyDomain>
<DataPropertyDomain>
  <DataProperty IRI="#hasLinguistics"/>
  <Class IRI="#Term"/>

```

```

</DataPropertyDomain>
<DataPropertyDomain>
  <DataProperty IRI="#hasPlural"/>
  <Class IRI="#Term"/>
</DataPropertyDomain>
<DataPropertyDomain>
  <DataProperty IRI="#hasSingular"/>
  <Class IRI="#Term"/>
</DataPropertyDomain>
<DataPropertyDomain>
  <DataProperty IRI="#hasWebResource"/>
  <Class IRI="#Term"/>
</DataPropertyDomain>
<DataPropertyRange>
  <DataProperty IRI="#hasAcronym"/>
  <Datatype abbreviatedIRI="xsd:string"/>
</DataPropertyRange>
<DataPropertyRange>
  <DataProperty IRI="#hasExplanation"/>
  <Datatype abbreviatedIRI="xsd:string"/>
</DataPropertyRange>
<DataPropertyRange>
  <DataProperty IRI="#hasGerund"/>
  <Datatype abbreviatedIRI="xsd:string"/>
</DataPropertyRange>
<DataPropertyRange>
  <DataProperty IRI="#hasIllegalAbbreviation"/>
  <Datatype abbreviatedIRI="xsd:string"/>
</DataPropertyRange>
<DataPropertyRange>
  <DataProperty IRI="#hasLinguistics"/>
  <Datatype abbreviatedIRI="xsd:string"/>
</DataPropertyRange>
<DataPropertyRange>
  <DataProperty IRI="#hasPlural"/>
  <Datatype abbreviatedIRI="xsd:string"/>
</DataPropertyRange>
<DataPropertyRange>
  <DataProperty IRI="#hasSingular"/>
  <Datatype abbreviatedIRI="xsd:string"/>
</DataPropertyRange>
<DataPropertyRange>
  <DataProperty IRI="#hasWebResource"/>
  <Datatype abbreviatedIRI="xsd:anyURI"/>
</DataPropertyRange>
</Ontology>

```

Appendix F-2 TermAnalyser.owl

```
<?xml version="1.0"?>

<!DOCTYPE Ontology [
  <!ENTITY xsd "http://www.w3.org/2001/XMLSchema#" >
  <!ENTITY xml "http://www.w3.org/XML/1998/namespace" >
  <!ENTITY rdfs "http://www.w3.org/2000/01/rdf-schema#" >
  <!ENTITY rdf "http://www.w3.org/1999/02/22-rdf-syntax-ns#" >
]

<Ontology xmlns="http://www.w3.org/2002/07/owl#"
  xml:base="http://owl-bva.appspot.com/TermAnalyser.owl"
  xmlns:rdfs="http://www.w3.org/2000/01/rdf-schema#"
  xmlns:xsd="http://www.w3.org/2001/XMLSchema#"
  xmlns:rdf="http://www.w3.org/1999/02/22-rdf-syntax-ns#"
  xmlns:xml="http://www.w3.org/XML/1998/namespace"
  ontologyIRI="http://owl-bva.appspot.com/TermAnalyser.owl">
  <Prefix name="xsd" IRI="http://www.w3.org/2001/XMLSchema#" />
  <Prefix name="owl" IRI="http://www.w3.org/2002/07/owl#" />
  <Prefix name="" IRI="http://www.w3.org/2002/07/owl#" />
  <Prefix name="rdf" IRI="http://www.w3.org/1999/02/22-rdf-syntax-ns#" />
  <Prefix name="rdfs" IRI="http://www.w3.org/2000/01/rdf-schema#" />
  <Import>http://owl-bva.appspot.com/EVA.owl</Import>
  <Declaration>
    <Class IRI="#TA-AccuracyAnalysedTerm" />
  </Declaration>
  <Declaration>
    <Class IRI="#TA-AnalyserConcept" />
  </Declaration>
  <Declaration>
    <Class IRI="#TA-AveragelyAccurateTerm" />
  </Declaration>
  <Declaration>
    <Class IRI="#TA-AveragelyUsefulTerm" />
  </Declaration>
  <Declaration>
    <Class IRI="#TA-ComplexTerm" />
  </Declaration>
  <Declaration>
    <Class IRI="#TA-ExpandedAcronymTerm" />
  </Declaration>
  <Declaration>
    <Class IRI="#TA-IllegalTerm" />
  </Declaration>
  <Declaration>
    <Class IRI="#TA-MultiAcronymTerm" />
  </Declaration>
  <Declaration>
    <Class IRI="#TA-MultiGerundTerm" />
  </Declaration>
  <Declaration>
    <Class IRI="#TA-MultiPluralityTerm" />
  </Declaration>
  <Declaration>
    <Class IRI="#TA-MultivaluedPropertyTerm" />
  </Declaration>
  <Declaration>
    <Class IRI="#TA-NotAccurateTerm" />
  </Declaration>
  <Declaration>
    <Class IRI="#TA-NotUsefulTerm" />
  </Declaration>
  <Declaration>
    <Class IRI="#TA-Term" />
  </Declaration>
  <Declaration>
    <Class IRI="#TA-UsefulnessAnalysedTerm" />
  </Declaration>
  <Declaration>
    <Class IRI="#TA-VeryAccurateTerm" />
  </Declaration>
  <Declaration>
    <Class IRI="#TA-VeryUsefulTerm" />
  </Declaration>
</Ontology>
```

```

</Declaration>
<Declaration>
  <DataProperty IRI="#hasAccuracyScore"/>
</Declaration>
<Declaration>
  <DataProperty IRI="#hasNegativeAccuracyCount"/>
</Declaration>
<Declaration>
  <DataProperty IRI="#hasNegativeUsefulnessCount"/>
</Declaration>
<Declaration>
  <DataProperty IRI="#hasPositiveAccuracyCount"/>
</Declaration>
<Declaration>
  <DataProperty IRI="#hasPositiveUsefulnessCount"/>
</Declaration>
<Declaration>
  <DataProperty IRI="#hasUsefulnessScore"/>
</Declaration>
<EquivalentClasses>
  <Class IRI="http://owl-bva.appspot.com/BVA.owl#Term"/>
  <Class IRI="#TA-Term"/>
</EquivalentClasses>
<EquivalentClasses>
  <Class IRI="#TA-AccuracyAnalysedTerm"/>
  <ObjectIntersectionOf>
    <Class IRI="#TA-Term"/>
    <DataSomeValuesFrom>
      <DataProperty IRI="#hasAccuracyScore"/>
      <Datatype abbreviatedIRI="xsd:unsignedInt"/>
    </DataSomeValuesFrom>
  </ObjectIntersectionOf>
</EquivalentClasses>
<EquivalentClasses>
  <Class IRI="#TA-AveragelyAccurateTerm"/>
  <DataSomeValuesFrom>
    <DataProperty IRI="#hasAccuracyScore"/>
    <DatatypeRestriction>
      <Datatype abbreviatedIRI="xsd:unsignedInt"/>
      <FacetRestriction facet="xsd:maxInclusive">
        <Literal datatypeIRI="xsd:unsignedInt">70</Literal>
      </FacetRestriction>
      <FacetRestriction facet="xsd:minExclusive">
        <Literal datatypeIRI="xsd:unsignedInt">30</Literal>
      </FacetRestriction>
    </DatatypeRestriction>
  </DataSomeValuesFrom>
</EquivalentClasses>
<EquivalentClasses>
  <Class IRI="#TA-AveragelyUsefulTerm"/>
  <DataSomeValuesFrom>
    <DataProperty IRI="#hasUsefulnessScore"/>
    <DatatypeRestriction>
      <Datatype abbreviatedIRI="xsd:unsignedInt"/>
      <FacetRestriction facet="xsd:maxInclusive">
        <Literal datatypeIRI="xsd:unsignedInt">70</Literal>
      </FacetRestriction>
      <FacetRestriction facet="xsd:minExclusive">
        <Literal datatypeIRI="xsd:unsignedInt">30</Literal>
      </FacetRestriction>
    </DatatypeRestriction>
  </DataSomeValuesFrom>
</EquivalentClasses>
<EquivalentClasses>
  <Class IRI="#TA-ComplexTerm"/>
  <ObjectIntersectionOf>
    <Class IRI="#TA-Term"/>
    <DataSomeValuesFrom>
      <DataProperty IRI="http://owl-bva.appspot.com/BVA.owl#hasExplanation"/>
      <Datatype abbreviatedIRI="xsd:string"/>
    </DataSomeValuesFrom>
  </ObjectIntersectionOf>
</EquivalentClasses>
<EquivalentClasses>
  <Class IRI="#TA-ExpandedAcronymTerm"/>
  <ObjectIntersectionOf>
    <Class IRI="#TA-Term"/>

```

```

        <DataSomeValuesFrom>
          <DataProperty IRI="http://owl-bva.appspot.com/BVA.owl#hasAcronym"/>
            <Datatype abbreviatedIRI="xsd:string"/>
          </DataSomeValuesFrom>
        </ObjectIntersectionOf>
      </EquivalentClasses>
    </EquivalentClasses>
    <EquivalentClasses>
      <Class IRI="#TA-IllegalTerm"/>
      <ObjectIntersectionOf>
        <Class IRI="#TA-Term"/>
        <ObjectSomeValuesFrom>
          <ObjectProperty
            IRI="http://owl-bva.appspot.com/BVA.owl#hasPreferredTerm"/>
          <Class IRI="#TA-Term"/>
        </ObjectSomeValuesFrom>
      </ObjectIntersectionOf>
    </EquivalentClasses>
  </EquivalentClasses>
  <EquivalentClasses>
    <Class IRI="#TA-MultiAcronymTerm"/>
    <ObjectIntersectionOf>
      <Class IRI="#TA-MultivaluedPropertyTerm"/>
      <DataMinCardinality cardinality="2">
        <DataProperty IRI="http://owl-bva.appspot.com/BVA.owl#hasAcronym"/>
      </DataMinCardinality>
    </ObjectIntersectionOf>
  </EquivalentClasses>
  <EquivalentClasses>
    <Class IRI="#TA-MultiGerundTerm"/>
    <ObjectIntersectionOf>
      <Class IRI="#TA-MultivaluedPropertyTerm"/>
      <DataMinCardinality cardinality="2">
        <DataProperty IRI="http://owl-bva.appspot.com/BVA.owl#hasGerund"/>
      </DataMinCardinality>
    </ObjectIntersectionOf>
  </EquivalentClasses>
  <EquivalentClasses>
    <Class IRI="#TA-MultiPluralityTerm"/>
    <ObjectIntersectionOf>
      <Class IRI="#TA-MultivaluedPropertyTerm"/>
      <DataMinCardinality cardinality="2">
        <DataProperty IRI="http://owl-bva.appspot.com/BVA.owl#hasPlural"/>
      </DataMinCardinality>
    </ObjectIntersectionOf>
  </EquivalentClasses>
  <EquivalentClasses>
    <Class IRI="#TA-MultivaluedPropertyTerm"/>
    <ObjectIntersectionOf>
      <Class IRI="#TA-Term"/>
      <DataMinCardinality cardinality="2">
        <DataProperty IRI="http://owl-bva.appspot.com/BVA.owl#hasLinguistics"/>
      </DataMinCardinality>
    </ObjectIntersectionOf>
  </EquivalentClasses>
  <EquivalentClasses>
    <Class IRI="#TA-NotAccurateTerm"/>
    <DataSomeValuesFrom>
      <DataProperty IRI="#hasAccuracyScore"/>
      <DatatypeRestriction>
        <Datatype abbreviatedIRI="xsd:unsignedInt"/>
        <FacetRestriction facet="&xsd;maxInclusive">
          <Literal datatypeIRI="&xsd;unsignedInt">30</Literal>
        </FacetRestriction>
      </DatatypeRestriction>
    </DataSomeValuesFrom>
  </EquivalentClasses>
  <EquivalentClasses>
    <Class IRI="#TA-NotUsefulTerm"/>
    <DataSomeValuesFrom>
      <DataProperty IRI="#hasUsefulnessScore"/>
      <DatatypeRestriction>
        <Datatype abbreviatedIRI="xsd:unsignedInt"/>
        <FacetRestriction facet="&xsd;maxInclusive">
          <Literal datatypeIRI="&xsd;unsignedInt">30</Literal>
        </FacetRestriction>
      </DatatypeRestriction>
    </DataSomeValuesFrom>
  </EquivalentClasses>

```

```

<EquivalentClasses>
  <Class IRI="#TA-UsefulnessAnalysedTerm"/>
  <ObjectIntersectionOf>
    <Class IRI="#TA-Term"/>
    <DataSomeValuesFrom>
      <DataProperty IRI="#hasUsefulnessScore"/>
      <Datatype abbreviatedIRI="xsd:unsignedInt"/>
    </DataSomeValuesFrom>
  </ObjectIntersectionOf>
</EquivalentClasses>
<EquivalentClasses>
  <Class IRI="#TA-VeryAccurateTerm"/>
  <DataSomeValuesFrom>
    <DataProperty IRI="#hasAccuracyScore"/>
    <DatatypeRestriction>
      <Datatype abbreviatedIRI="xsd:unsignedInt"/>
      <FacetRestriction facet="&xsd;minExclusive">
        <Literal datatypeIRI="&xsd;unsignedInt">70</Literal>
      </FacetRestriction>
    </DatatypeRestriction>
  </DataSomeValuesFrom>
</EquivalentClasses>
<EquivalentClasses>
  <Class IRI="#TA-VeryUsefulTerm"/>
  <DataSomeValuesFrom>
    <DataProperty IRI="#hasUsefulnessScore"/>
    <DatatypeRestriction>
      <Datatype abbreviatedIRI="xsd:unsignedInt"/>
      <FacetRestriction facet="&xsd;minExclusive">
        <Literal datatypeIRI="&xsd;unsignedInt">70</Literal>
      </FacetRestriction>
    </DatatypeRestriction>
  </DataSomeValuesFrom>
</EquivalentClasses>
<SubClassOf>
  <Class IRI="#TA-AccuracyAnalysedTerm"/>
  <Class IRI="#TA-Term"/>
</SubClassOf>
<SubClassOf>
  <Class IRI="#TA-AveragelyAccurateTerm"/>
  <Class IRI="#TA-AccuracyAnalysedTerm"/>
</SubClassOf>
<SubClassOf>
  <Class IRI="#TA-AveragelyUsefulTerm"/>
  <Class IRI="#TA-UsefulnessAnalysedTerm"/>
</SubClassOf>
<SubClassOf>
  <Class IRI="#TA-ComplexTerm"/>
  <Class IRI="#TA-Term"/>
</SubClassOf>
<SubClassOf>
  <Class IRI="#TA-ExpandedAcronymTerm"/>
  <Class IRI="#TA-Term"/>
</SubClassOf>
<SubClassOf>
  <Class IRI="#TA-IllegalTerm"/>
  <Class IRI="#TA-Term"/>
</SubClassOf>
<SubClassOf>
  <Class IRI="#TA-MultiAcronymTerm"/>
  <Class IRI="#TA-MultivaluedPropertyTerm"/>
</SubClassOf>
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  <Class IRI="#TA-MultiGerundTerm"/>
  <Class IRI="#TA-MultivaluedPropertyTerm"/>
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<SubClassOf>
  <Class IRI="#TA-MultiPluralityTerm"/>
  <Class IRI="#TA-MultivaluedPropertyTerm"/>
</SubClassOf>
<SubClassOf>
  <Class IRI="#TA-MultivaluedPropertyTerm"/>
  <Class IRI="#TA-Term"/>
</SubClassOf>
<SubClassOf>
  <Class IRI="#TA-NotAccurateTerm"/>
  <Class IRI="#TA-AccuracyAnalysedTerm"/>

```

```

</SubClassOf>
<SubClassOf>
  <Class IRI="#TA-NotUsefulTerm"/>
  <Class IRI="#TA-UsefulnessAnalysedTerm"/>
</SubClassOf>
<SubClassOf>
  <Class IRI="#TA-Term"/>
  <Class IRI="#TA-AnalyserConcept"/>
</SubClassOf>
<SubClassOf>
  <Class IRI="#TA-UsefulnessAnalysedTerm"/>
  <Class IRI="#TA-Term"/>
</SubClassOf>
<SubClassOf>
  <Class IRI="#TA-VeryAccurateTerm"/>
  <Class IRI="#TA-AccuracyAnalysedTerm"/>
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  <Class IRI="#TA-VeryUsefulTerm"/>
  <Class IRI="#TA-UsefulnessAnalysedTerm"/>
</SubClassOf>
<DataPropertyAssertion>
  <DataProperty IRI="#hasAccuracyScore"/>
  <NamedIndividual
IRI="http://owl-bva.appspot.com/BVA.owl#term-Physical_Products"/>
  <Literal datatypeIRI="&xsd;unsignedInt">80</Literal>
</DataPropertyAssertion>
<DataPropertyAssertion>
  <DataProperty IRI="#hasNegativeAccuracyCount"/>
  <NamedIndividual
IRI="http://owl-bva.appspot.com/BVA.owl#term-Physical_Products"/>
  <Literal datatypeIRI="&xsd;unsignedInt">1</Literal>
</DataPropertyAssertion>
<DataPropertyAssertion>
  <DataProperty IRI="#hasNegativeUsefulnessCount"/>
  <NamedIndividual
IRI="http://owl-bva.appspot.com/BVA.owl#term-Physical_Products"/>
  <Literal datatypeIRI="&xsd;unsignedInt">1</Literal>
</DataPropertyAssertion>
<DataPropertyAssertion>
  <DataProperty IRI="#hasPositiveAccuracyCount"/>
  <NamedIndividual
IRI="http://owl-bva.appspot.com/BVA.owl#term-Physical_Products"/>
  <Literal datatypeIRI="&xsd;unsignedInt">4</Literal>
</DataPropertyAssertion>
<DataPropertyAssertion>
  <DataProperty IRI="#hasPositiveUsefulnessCount"/>
  <NamedIndividual
IRI="http://owl-bva.appspot.com/BVA.owl#term-Physical_Products"/>
  <Literal datatypeIRI="&xsd;unsignedInt">1</Literal>
</DataPropertyAssertion>
<DataPropertyAssertion>
  <DataProperty IRI="#hasUsefulnessScore"/>
  <NamedIndividual
IRI="http://owl-bva.appspot.com/BVA.owl#term-Physical_Products"/>
  <Literal datatypeIRI="&xsd;unsignedInt">50</Literal>
</DataPropertyAssertion>
<DataPropertyAssertion>
  <DataProperty IRI="#hasAccuracyScore"/>
  <NamedIndividual
IRI="http://owl-bva.appspot.com/BVA.owl#term-Professional_Sales_Skill"/>
  <Literal datatypeIRI="&xsd;unsignedInt">70</Literal>
</DataPropertyAssertion>
<DataPropertyAssertion>
  <DataProperty IRI="#hasNegativeAccuracyCount"/>
  <NamedIndividual
IRI="http://owl-bva.appspot.com/BVA.owl#term-Professional_Sales_Skill"/>
  <Literal datatypeIRI="&xsd;unsignedInt">6</Literal>
</DataPropertyAssertion>
<DataPropertyAssertion>
  <DataProperty IRI="#hasNegativeUsefulnessCount"/>
  <NamedIndividual
IRI="http://owl-bva.appspot.com/BVA.owl#term-Professional_Sales_Skill"/>
  <Literal datatypeIRI="&xsd;unsignedInt">1</Literal>
</DataPropertyAssertion>
<DataPropertyAssertion>
  <DataProperty IRI="#hasPositiveAccuracyCount"/>

```

```

    <NamedIndividual
IRI="http://owl-bva.appspot.com/BVA.owl#term-Professional_Sales_Skill"/>
    <Literal datatypeIRI="&xsd;unsignedInt">14</Literal>
  </DataPropertyAssertion>
  <DataPropertyAssertion>
    <DataProperty IRI="#hasPositiveUsefulnessCount"/>
    <NamedIndividual
IRI="http://owl-bva.appspot.com/BVA.owl#term-Professional_Sales_Skill"/>
    <Literal datatypeIRI="&xsd;unsignedInt">5</Literal>
  </DataPropertyAssertion>
  <DataPropertyAssertion>
    <DataProperty IRI="#hasUsefulnessScore"/>
    <NamedIndividual
IRI="http://owl-bva.appspot.com/BVA.owl#term-Professional_Sales_Skill"/>
    <Literal datatypeIRI="&xsd;unsignedInt">83</Literal>
  </DataPropertyAssertion>
  <DataPropertyDomain>
    <DataProperty IRI="#hasAccuracyScore"/>
    <Class IRI="#TA-Term"/>
  </DataPropertyDomain>
  <DataPropertyDomain>
    <DataProperty IRI="#hasNegativeAccuracyCount"/>
    <Class IRI="#TA-Term"/>
  </DataPropertyDomain>
  <DataPropertyDomain>
    <DataProperty IRI="#hasNegativeUsefulnessCount"/>
    <Class IRI="#TA-Term"/>
  </DataPropertyDomain>
  <DataPropertyDomain>
    <DataProperty IRI="#hasPositiveAccuracyCount"/>
    <Class IRI="#TA-Term"/>
  </DataPropertyDomain>
  <DataPropertyDomain>
    <DataProperty IRI="#hasPositiveUsefulnessCount"/>
    <Class IRI="#TA-Term"/>
  </DataPropertyDomain>
  <DataPropertyDomain>
    <DataProperty IRI="#hasUsefulnessScore"/>
    <Class IRI="#TA-Term"/>
  </DataPropertyDomain>
  <DataPropertyRange>
    <DataProperty IRI="#hasAccuracyScore"/>
    <DatatypeRestriction>
      <Datatype abbreviatedIRI="xsd:unsignedInt"/>
      <FacetRestriction facet="&xsd;maxInclusive">
        <Literal datatypeIRI="&xsd;integer">100</Literal>
      </FacetRestriction>
    </DatatypeRestriction>
  </DataPropertyRange>
  <DataPropertyRange>
    <DataProperty IRI="#hasNegativeAccuracyCount"/>
    <Datatype abbreviatedIRI="xsd:unsignedInt"/>
  </DataPropertyRange>
  <DataPropertyRange>
    <DataProperty IRI="#hasNegativeUsefulnessCount"/>
    <Datatype abbreviatedIRI="xsd:unsignedInt"/>
  </DataPropertyRange>
  <DataPropertyRange>
    <DataProperty IRI="#hasPositiveAccuracyCount"/>
    <Datatype abbreviatedIRI="xsd:unsignedInt"/>
  </DataPropertyRange>
  <DataPropertyRange>
    <DataProperty IRI="#hasPositiveUsefulnessCount"/>
    <Datatype abbreviatedIRI="xsd:unsignedInt"/>
  </DataPropertyRange>
  <DataPropertyRange>
    <DataProperty IRI="#hasUsefulnessScore"/>
    <DatatypeRestriction>
      <Datatype abbreviatedIRI="xsd:unsignedInt"/>
      <FacetRestriction facet="&xsd;maxInclusive">
        <Literal datatypeIRI="&xsd;integer">100</Literal>
      </FacetRestriction>
    </DatatypeRestriction>
  </DataPropertyRange>
</Ontology>

```


Appendix F-3 TermTester.owl

```
<?xml version="1.0"?>

<!DOCTYPE Ontology [
  <!ENTITY xsd "http://www.w3.org/2001/XMLSchema#" >
  <!ENTITY xml "http://www.w3.org/XML/1998/namespace" >
  <!ENTITY rdfs "http://www.w3.org/2000/01/rdf-schema#" >
  <!ENTITY rdf "http://www.w3.org/1999/02/22-rdf-syntax-ns#" >
]

<Ontology xmlns="http://www.w3.org/2002/07/owl#"
  xml:base="http://owl-bva.appspot.com/TermTester.owl"
  xmlns:rdfs="http://www.w3.org/2000/01/rdf-schema#"
  xmlns:xsd="http://www.w3.org/2001/XMLSchema#"
  xmlns:rdf="http://www.w3.org/1999/02/22-rdf-syntax-ns#"
  xmlns:xml="http://www.w3.org/XML/1998/namespace"
  ontologyIRI="http://owl-bva.appspot.com/TermTester.owl">
  <Prefix name="xsd" IRI="http://www.w3.org/2001/XMLSchema#" />
  <Prefix name="owl" IRI="http://www.w3.org/2002/07/owl#" />
  <Prefix name="" IRI="http://www.w3.org/2002/07/owl#" />
  <Prefix name="rdf" IRI="http://www.w3.org/1999/02/22-rdf-syntax-ns#" />
  <Prefix name="rdfs" IRI="http://www.w3.org/2000/01/rdf-schema#" />
  <Import>http://owl-bva.appspot.com/BVA.owl</Import>
  <Import>http://owl-bva.appspot.com/TermAnalyser.owl</Import>
  <Declaration>
    <Class IRI="#TT-ExcessiveAcronymTerm" />
  </Declaration>
  <Declaration>
    <Class IRI="#TT-MultipleSingularityTerm" />
  </Declaration>
  <Declaration>
    <Class IRI="#TT-Term" />
  </Declaration>
  <Declaration>
    <Class IRI="#TT-TestConcept" />
  </Declaration>
  <Declaration>
    <Class IRI="#TT-TestTerm" />
  </Declaration>
  <Declaration>
    <NamedIndividual IRI="#TT-term-Excessive_Acronyms" />
  </Declaration>
  <Declaration>
    <NamedIndividual IRI="#TT-term-Too_Many_Singulars" />
  </Declaration>
  <EquivalentClasses>
    <Class IRI="http://owl-bva.appspot.com/BVA.owl#Term" />
    <Class IRI="#TT-Term" />
  </EquivalentClasses>
  <EquivalentClasses>
    <Class IRI="#TT-ExcessiveAcronymTerm" />
    <ObjectIntersectionOf>
      <Class IRI="#TT-Term" />
      <DataMinCardinality cardinality="5">
        <DataProperty IRI="http://owl-bva.appspot.com/BVA.owl#hasAcronym" />
      </DataMinCardinality>
    </ObjectIntersectionOf>
  </EquivalentClasses>
  <EquivalentClasses>
    <Class IRI="#TT-MultipleSingularityTerm" />
    <ObjectIntersectionOf>
      <Class IRI="#TT-Term" />
      <DataMinCardinality cardinality="2">
        <DataProperty IRI="http://owl-bva.appspot.com/BVA.owl#hasSingular" />
      </DataMinCardinality>
    </ObjectIntersectionOf>
  </EquivalentClasses>
  <SubClassOf>
    <Class IRI="#TT-ExcessiveAcronymTerm" />
    <Class IRI="#TT-Term" />
  </SubClassOf>
  <SubClassOf>
    <Class IRI="#TT-MultipleSingularityTerm" />
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    <Class IRI="#TT-Term"/>
  </SubClassOf>
  <SubClassOf>
    <Class IRI="#TT-Term"/>
    <Class IRI="#TT-TestConcept"/>
  </SubClassOf>
  <SubClassOf>
    <Class IRI="#TT-TestTerm"/>
    <Class IRI="#TT-TestConcept"/>
  </SubClassOf>
  <ClassAssertion>
    <Class IRI="#TT-TestTerm"/>
    <NamedIndividual IRI="#TT-term-Excessive_Acronyms"/>
  </ClassAssertion>
  <ClassAssertion>
    <Class IRI="#TT-TestTerm"/>
    <NamedIndividual IRI="#TT-term-Too_Many_Singulars"/>
  </ClassAssertion>
  <DataPropertyAssertion>
    <DataProperty IRI="http://owl-bva.appspot.com/BVA.owl#hasAcronym"/>
    <NamedIndividual IRI="#TT-term-Excessive_Acronyms"/>
    <Literal datatypeIRI="&xsd:string">AAB</Literal>
  </DataPropertyAssertion>
  <DataPropertyAssertion>
    <DataProperty IRI="http://owl-bva.appspot.com/BVA.owl#hasAcronym"/>
    <NamedIndividual IRI="#TT-term-Excessive_Acronyms"/>
    <Literal datatypeIRI="&xsd:string">AAA</Literal>
  </DataPropertyAssertion>
  <DataPropertyAssertion>
    <DataProperty IRI="http://owl-bva.appspot.com/BVA.owl#hasAcronym"/>
    <NamedIndividual IRI="#TT-term-Excessive_Acronyms"/>
    <Literal datatypeIRI="&xsd:string">AAE</Literal>
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  <DataPropertyAssertion>
    <DataProperty IRI="http://owl-bva.appspot.com/BVA.owl#hasAcronym"/>
    <NamedIndividual IRI="#TT-term-Excessive_Acronyms"/>
    <Literal datatypeIRI="&xsd:string">AAC</Literal>
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  <DataPropertyAssertion>
    <DataProperty IRI="http://owl-bva.appspot.com/BVA.owl#hasAcronym"/>
    <NamedIndividual IRI="#TT-term-Excessive_Acronyms"/>
    <Literal datatypeIRI="&xsd:string">AAD</Literal>
  </DataPropertyAssertion>
  <DataPropertyAssertion>
    <DataProperty IRI="http://owl-bva.appspot.com/BVA.owl#hasSingular"/>
    <NamedIndividual IRI="#TT-term-Too_Many_Singulars"/>
    <Literal datatypeIRI="&xsd:string">singular string one</Literal>
  </DataPropertyAssertion>
  <DataPropertyAssertion>
    <DataProperty IRI="http://owl-bva.appspot.com/BVA.owl#hasSingular"/>
    <NamedIndividual IRI="#TT-term-Too_Many_Singulars"/>
    <Literal datatypeIRI="&xsd:string">singular string two</Literal>
  </DataPropertyAssertion>
</Ontology>

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